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1. Introduction

This is a report on adaptation and mitigation tools and strategies to address the risks from permafrost thaw in communities along the Arctic coasts. The report presents first an overview of the impacts of permafrost thaw and measures of adaptation at the local level in Arctic coastal communities. Mitigation measures are perceived and presented here as a subset of adaptation strategies for addressing the risks posed by thawing permafrost, including highly concentrated measures to preserve permafrost or reduce permafrost thaw, e.g., by insulating the ground from the heat of a building, pipes, asphalt and air or by means of mechanized refrigeration or thermosyphons, as well as the efforts to reduce emission of greenhouse gasses, e.g., by adopting renewable energy and furnishing buildings to make them more energy efficient. The adaptation measures fall under the heading of financial investments; construction measures; technology and communication means: modification of mobility patterns; investment in training, education, and capacity; modification of energy, food and water provision practices; modification of regulatory and planning frameworks; monitoring, testing and forecasting; and socio-cultural changes. This is followed by a literature review and a methods section, linking the adaptation report to a risk framework developed earlier in the Nunataryuk process (a Compass Model and Methodological Flow Chart) (see Larsen et al. 2021).

The development of this framework was motivated by observations and perceptions that thawing permafrost creates risks to the environment, economy, and culture of affected Arctic coastal communities. More effective identification of these risks and the inclusion of the societal context and co-production with local stakeholders can provide the basis for effective risk management, reduced risks, more effective adaptation, and a more sustainable future (Larsen et al. 2021; 2022). A central element within the risk framework presented is the notion of the dual dimensions of risk – the recognition of risk as both physical and socially constructed – and the importance of risk perceptions of permafrost affected Arctic communities, and in turn the co-production of knowledge. This framework has guided the co-production of knowledge between Nunataryuk researchers and local stakeholders on adaptation and mitigation within our case study regions and served as the point of departure for extensive discussions on not only existing and possible future tools, but also questions related to factors presenting constraints to effective adaptation at the local level.

We provide results from extensive stakeholder engagement and co-production in four case study regions along the Arctic Coast; Ilulissat and Qeqertarsuaq, West Greenland; Longyearbyen, Svalbard; Beaufort Sea Region, Yukon Coast and Mackenzie River Delta; and Northern Sakha (Yakutiya), Russia. We first present the results from a survey on adaptation strategies that was conducted in the case study regions in 2019 (not including Russia), and with a slightly modified version of the survey conducted in Ilulissat in 2023. Next, we present and discuss local specific adaptation data from research conducted within all case study areas, including existing adaptation measures and other solutions being discussed at the local level. We conclude with a general discussion and some reflections on the tools and effectiveness of adaptation, and the prospects for future sustainability in the local coastal communities studied.

2. Overview of adaptation and mitigation measures

Permafrost thaw requires costly risk management and adaptation measures, such as hazard prevention and innovative engineering techniques (foundation upgrades, flood control, etc.). Maintenance and construction practices must be adapted to Arctic weather, local permafrost conditions, and predicted climatic and environmental changes. Thawing permafrost, resulting in increased slumping and riverbank erosion, also forces land users to travel longer distances or to modify their routes and means of transportation. Improved communication among monitoring entities, scientists, and community members, along with the use of new technology and communication methods, enhances land user safety. Moreover, effective recruitment, retention, and training of medical, engineering, scientific, and administrative personnel strengthen community preparedness for emerging challenges.

Diversifying and adapting food, water, and energy provision, while ensuring import quality and flexibility, further enhances security in Arctic communities. Governance-related adaptation measures involve, for example, investing in Indigenous and local knowledge, adapting regulatory frameworks, and establishing emergency preparedness protocols. Also, thawing permafrost may require more investment in community-based monitoring, disease control, or testing and regulating practices. Permafrost thaw as a symptom of global warming leads to changes in symbolic culture, social organization and behavior, such as adapting knowledge transfer and cultural learning. Last but not least, mitigating climate change requires reducing greenhouse gas concentrations and emissions of contaminants, especially in industrialized nations.

Figure 1: “Actions needed” Graphic produced in collaboration with Grid Arendal / Levi Westerveld 2023.

The graphic above shows all sectors in which adaptation actions can be taken. The following section provides some examples for each adaptation action group. Note, that this list is not exhaustive, but it shows the wide variety and many options that are being taken or can be recommended. The information presented here was gathered throughout the risk analysis process.

FINANCIAL INVESTMENTS:

- In the case of inadequate engineering, investing more funds for better constructions. Investment in adaptation and protective measures such as: Removal, Repair, Relocation (of individual houses/cabins within communities and of communities) and Innovation for e.g., sustainable Rebuilding, developing new construction materials etc.
- Investment in and Training for (Community-Based) monitoring, including adaptation of monitoring techniques; i.e., by usage of drones

CONSTRUCTION MEASURES

- Governance adaptation measures include investing in Indigenous and local knowledge and co-management, adapting regulatory frameworks, and establishing emergency preparedness protocols, for example
- Building new infrastructure, for i.e., flood control
- Repairing and/or building new roads etc.
- Building sustainable water and energy supply facilities
- Piling and foundation measures
- Innovation in, e.g., sustainable (re-)building, new construction materials, etc.

TECHNOLOGY & COMMUNICATION MEANS

- Adapting technology & communication, i.e. using GPS and phones to ensure communication and letting people know where you are going on the land
- Employing and developing environmental monitoring systems such as: remote sensing, laser scanners, drones etc.
- Adapting hunting, fishing and herding techniques, such as i.e. using different tools
- Increasing community engagement and enhance communication strategies between governance structures and communities, as well as within communities themselves
- Bridging the science-community gap

MODIFICATION OF MOBILITY PATTERNS

- Modification of travel routes
- Modification of transportation means, e.g., using skidoos instead of ATVs, walking instead of using fuel-powered machines, and reviving techniques such as traveling with sled dogs, boats etc.

INVESTMENT IN TRAINING, EDUCATION & CAPACITY

- Using and developing appropriate engineering practices

- Finding, retaining and training of medical, engineering, administrative and scientific personnel
- Invest in and Training for (especially Community-Based) monitoring, including training for new technologies
- Activating and fostering social networks for help
- Educating local population on risks and emergency responses
- Enhancing collaboration and mutual capacity building between administration, communities and researchers
- Establishing long-term measures and systems to ensure knowledge and skills transfer (in Indigenous and transient communities)
- Investing in local and Indigenous knowledge and languages to strengthen identity, resilience, wellbeing
- Strengthening and integrating local (Indigenous) knowledge, culture and language in e.g., monitoring practices, land use planning, and regulatory frameworks
- Educating and training social and health sector about permafrost thaw and climate change in general
- Finding, retaining and training of medical personnel
- Establishing (therapeutic) counselors and support groups
- Establishing security protocols for being on the land, and construction
- Updating list of monitoring contaminants and diseases (for example in connection with Arctic Council Working Group Activities)

MODIFICATION OF ENERGY, FOOD & WATER PROVISION PRACTICES

- Developing (renewable) energy supply targeting energy security and independence
- Adapting subsistence techniques such as reindeer herding and hunting etc., such as e.g., changing time to hunt, or planning for and taking more time to hunt
- Finding new sources and adapt techniques for water provision, e.g., desalination
- Replacing food sources if necessary (moose hunting instead of caribou e.g., or changing fish species that are being fished)
- Rationing food sources, if necessary, e.g. eating less caribou
- Ensuring import quality and flexibility (also as part of emergency preparedness)
- Keeping supplies and backups of essential products and services
- Ensuring maintenance of storage facilities, including ice cellars, which are particularly prone to deterioration caused by permafrost thaw

The **Greenland** government is implementing standards and norms to provide an up-to-date and adequate regulatory framework for buildings and constructions.

North West Canada, Greenland and Svalbard are actively investing in developing alternative energy sources and in renewable energy, such as wind, hydro and solar power, to reduce carbon footprint.

On **Svalbard** new structures are built with adapted foundations, such as steel piles that are drilled deeper into the permafrost, and measures for protecting infrastructure below landslide prone slopes have been taken.

In **Inuvik**, experimental pilings and ground temperature monitors are used to test best practices in preserving the permafrost below buildings to maintain structural stability.

MODIFICATION OF REGULATORY & PLANNING FRAMEWORKS

- Create and/or adapt frameworks for regulations, e.g., to protect animals and plants, and react to changing migration patterns or habitat
- Adapt land use, community and urban planning to new needs caused by increased permafrost thaw
- Establish health emergency preparedness protocols
- Include concerns and knowledge about permafrost thaw in regulatory frameworks and planning policies

MONITORING, TESTING & FORECASTING

- Testing, purifying water
- Investing in and training for (Community-Based) monitoring, including adaptation of monitoring techniques; e.g., by use of drone
- Regulating water discharge
- Closing off areas
- Disease control, such as e.g., emergency slaughter and burning of infected animals

SOCIO-CULTURAL CHANGES

- Investing in cultural assets, local (Indigenous) knowledge and technologies to strengthen identity, resilience, wellbeing
- Strengthening and integrating local (Indigenous) knowledge, culture and language in e.g., monitoring practices, land use planning, construction techniques and regulatory frameworks
- Adapting inter-generational knowledge transfer and cultural norms
- Adapting symbolic culture, social structure and organization, and practices

Finally, mitigation of global warming requires the active **REDUCTION OF GREENHOUSE GAS CONCENTRATIONS** and emissions. The release of environmentally active contaminants, especially by industrialized nations, needs to be policed.

Results from the case study regions along the Arctic Coast in Ilulissat and Qeqertarsuaq (West Greenland), Longyearbyen (Svalbard), the Beaufort Sea Region, Yukon Coast and Mackenzie River Delta (Canada) and Northern Sakha (Yakutiya in Russia) show that a variety of adaptation measures exist while other solutions are being discussed at the local level. The following two sections discuss relevant literature and methods before the results specific to the above mentioned study sites are presented.

3. Literature review

Adaptation is at the same time a powerful buzzword in climate change policies and an analytical concept to study human-environment relations (Thornton & Manasfi 2010). It generally refers to “the processes by which individuals and groups of people adjust their behavior and organization in response to changes in their environment” (ibid.: 134). The concept of adaptation has a long history in anthropology: it originated in evolutionary theory and was further developed in ecological anthropology, mainly cultural ecology. In this latter paradigm adaptation refers to the ways that humans relate to the natural environment through culture: To the slow and large process by which human cultures diversify and change in relation to an ever-changing environment: “Adaptation has come to be understood as the process of development by which a community chooses to embrace a particular culture, subsistence system, pattern of resource use, etc. as one of several possible paths to be taken in its particular environment.” (Krupnik 1993: 18). Cultural change and development in this sense must not be confused with progress or be valued: “Change over time is not “good” or “bad”; it simply happens.” (Sutton & Anderson 2010: 12)

Humans adapt to the environment through both biological adaptation (on a much larger time-scale) and culture: “Culture is a way in which groups of people can adapt to the environment, through collective behavior and/or technology.” (ibid.: 12) “In essence,” then, “culture itself is an adaptive mechanism. Cultures contain a number of elements, such as social and political systems, settlement patterns, and technology and storage that are adaptive in their form and evolve as environments change.” (ibid.: 131) Even though the focus in much cultural ecological work is on the role of subsistence and technology, adaptation also takes place on the levels of social organization and culture (ibid.: 101). Cultural ecological approaches established that adaptations develop in response to changes in both the social and the natural environment: “Of course, any adaptive strategy is shaped, not only by the nature of the environment, but also by social values, cultural traditions, technological development, external influences, and a plethora of other factors.” (Krupnik 1993: 18) Environmental stressors such as climate changes thus need to be considered in their societal contexts, which is a central premise of anthropological approaches to climate change adaptation. Adaptation thus refers to how societies change and adjust in response to environmental changes: “As the environment changes, a society may be expected to adjust and readjust to these changes in its external conditions.” (Carneiro 2003: 180).

Anthropologists are currently revisiting the anthropological concept of adaptation to be applied in climate change research (see for instance Barnes et al. 2013; Crate 2008; Fiske et al. 2014; Head 2010; Nelson, West & Finan 2009; Oliver-Smith 2017; Thornton & Manasfi 2010). Acknowledging adaptation as a social process in response to both environmental and social, political, cultural and economic changes is essential in the anthropological understanding of adaptation (see, for instance Oliver-Smith 2017; Crate 2008; Thornton & Manasfi 2010). Anthropologists have thus criticized mainstream climate change literature and the way the concept is used in climate change policies for ignoring the complex nature of human adaptation in favor of an “analytical bias toward technological interventions and narrow behavioral responses to specific risks” (Nelson, West & Finan 2009: 272). Much of the mainstream adaptation literature considers climate change in isolation from other processes and is “focused on technologies and the elusive search for large-scale, cookie-cutter solutions, leaving aside the important role that individuals, cultures, and societies play in constructing and living out an adaptation dynamic” (ibid.: 272). In contrast, anthropologists call for a holistic definition of adaptation, including both material and cultural, objective and subjective aspects of adaptation (Oliver-Smith 2017), and constituted through diverse, intersecting processes, taking place on multiple scales in response to multiple climatic and non-climatic stressors (see also Thornton & Manasfi 2010):

Human adaptation to the natural environment is neither a biological nor a technical response of an undifferentiated population to physical or material conditions. It is always internally complex, involving the diverse interests, knowledge, and meanings of a differentiated population, interacting within both the material processes of a complex and dynamic physical setting and a set of social, political, economic, and ideological institutions and practices. (Oliver-Smith 2017: 206)

The importance of the cultural dimensions (shared worldviews, values, knowledges, customs and behaviors, etc.) shaping climate change adaptation (Adger et al. 2013; Barnes et al. 2013) are increasingly recognized also outside of anthropology (Few et al. 2020). Importantly, cultural

values, meanings and perceptions shape adaptation practices, as well as how the “idea of climate change” itself (Hulme 2009) is understood. Whether and how individuals and groups respond to climate change thus depends on “what the effects of climate change mean to those affected” (O’Brien & Wolf 2010: 232).

The expanding body of social science literature on climate change has identified various categories of adaptation which are useful in the analysis of adaptive processes. An important distinction is that between planned adaptation (“what humans must rationally do in order to reduce risk and vulnerability” (Thornton & Manasfi 2010: 133)) and autonomous adaptation, adaptations by individuals, households and businesses on the local level, that are “usually unnoticed, uncoordinated, and unaided by national governments, development agencies, or international agencies” (Christoplos et al. 2009: 3, cited in Thornton & Manasfi 2010: 133). In a similar vein, authors distinguish between centralized, top-down adaptation and bottom-up efforts that “stress engagement with community building and multi-level politics” (Oliver-Smith 2017: 213). A related distinction concerns the different levels of adaptation, including adaptations on the individual or household level, on the community level (Hovelsrud et al. 2010), adaptations that require larger-scale interactions and change within a broader governance network (Keskitalo & Kulyasova 2009), institutional adaptation (Ghorbani, Siddiki & Bravo 2023) and collective adaptation (Wannewitz & Garschagen 2023). Other ways of categorizing adaptations would be by form (technological, behavioral, institutional, etc.), and timing (anticipatory, reactive) (Thornton & Manasfi 2010: 136). Regarding the latter, reactive adaptation has been identified as “insufficient as a long-term strategy to meet many of the effects of cryospheric changes” and it has been argued that “proactive adaptation and strategies are urgently needed” (Hovelsrud et al. 2011: 101).

An important related concept is that of adaptive capacity, which refers to “the potential or ability of a system, region, or community to adapt by adjusting to, moderating the potential damages of, taking advantage of the opportunities created by, or coping with the effects of global climate change” (Crate 2008: 571). Different factors have been identified as contributing and determining adaptive capacity, such as economic resources, technology, information and skills, infrastructure, institutions and equity (Smit & Pilisofova 2001), although case studies reveal that these categories are often too broad to capture local specificities, which in the Arctic are often determined by degree of market integration and type of governance system (Keskitalo et al. 2011). Cultural factors such as acknowledgement of uncertainty and unpredictability, flexibility in resource use, and social capital have furthermore been identified as determining adaptability (Ford, McDowell & Pearce 2015: 1046). Importantly, local, traditional ecological, and place-based knowledge has been found to crucially determine adaptive capacity in the Arctic and elsewhere (Ford, McDowell & Pearce 2015; Naess 2013; Nakashima et al. 2012).

The concept of adaptation is often applied and discussed in connection to the related concepts of vulnerability and resilience, a framework that has been adopted, further developed, and criticized in anthropology (e.g. Crate 2008; Oliver-Smith 2017; Thornton & Manasfi 2010). This framework places climate change in the context of other changes affecting local communities and underlines the importance of the societal context in climate change research. The concept of vulnerability,

originating in the field of disaster research, describes the extent to which a system is susceptible to harm from environmental impacts, and implies that the impact of any physical event is determined by the social, economic, and cultural conditions of the affected society (Ford & Smit 2004; Turner et al. 2003). Within the climate change literature, vulnerability describes the extent to which a system is susceptible to harm from climate change, and it is considered to be a function of exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity (Ford & Furgal 2009; O'Brien et al. 2004). Anthropologists have adopted this term as it allows to study environmental impacts in specific societal contexts, and focus on the social factors that shape vulnerability (Marino 2015; Oliver-Smith 2017), stressing that vulnerability is “produced in and by society” (Ribot 2014: 667). Two different approaches or interpretations of vulnerability can be identified (O'Brien et al. 2007). While the “outcome” approach considers vulnerability simply a result of a particular physical stressor, the “contextual” approach regards vulnerability as “part of multidimensional, context-specific climate-society interactions” (Räsänen, Juhola & Nygren 2016, p. 2292). The latter thus considers both the economic, political, social and cultural conditions of the affected society and the socioeconomic and climatic changes that converge to create vulnerabilities, which makes it fruitful for the study of Arctic change (Hovelsrud et al. 2010).

4. Methods

Our Conceptual Risk Model, the so-called Compass Model, is an inductive framework based on community and scientific input. It proposes guidance to the identification of risk and consequent development of adaptation and mitigation strategies in large, multidisciplinary projects working in multiple field sites. Its goal is to assist the interaction between different components of scientific work and the needs of local communities. It works in parallel to the processual model (see below), by providing an attractive tool which can be used by different stakeholders for identifying key risks and the processes leading to them (Larsen et al. 2021; 2022).

Figure 2: The “Compass model”, a conceptual model to guide the identification of risks and the consequent development of adaptation and mitigation strategies in coproduction with local stakeholders (Larsen et al. 2021). Graphical illustration by Levi Westerveld—GRID-Arendal.

Our Processual Model, a Methodological Flow Chart (see below)—demonstrates how to implement what has been outlined in the conceptual model. It supports its users in the process of carrying out systematic data gathering. In our case, we worked in field sites in four countries – Canada, Greenland, Norway (Svalbard), and Russia) – collecting qualitative and quantitative data from a variety of natural and social science disciplines (Larsen et al. 2021).

Methodological flow chart

Figure 3: Methodological flow chart describing the implementation of the risk evaluation concept in the Nunataryuk project (Larsen et al. 2021). Graphical illustration by Levi Westerveld—GRID-Arendal.

The data collection, analysis and synthesis presented in this report was carried out collaboratively by a multidisciplinary group of researchers from the disciplines of various social sciences, health sciences and civil engineering, whose members have collectively conducted interdisciplinary fieldwork with a focus on risks of permafrost thaw in four regions of study: Ilulissat in West Greenland, Longyearbyen on Svalbard, the Northernmost area of Sakha in Russia, and Aklavik, Inuvik and Tuktoyaktuk in Northwestern Canada. The highly localized, heterogeneous physical processes of thawing ground pose several key hazards to local populations. These key hazards are infrastructure failure, disruption of mobility and supply, decrease in water quality, challenges for food security, and exposure to infectious diseases and contaminants. In turn, these key hazards have direct and indirect (perceived) consequences for various spheres of human lives including on culture & language, health & wellbeing, costs & economy, ecosystem (functioning), recreation & being in nature and planning & fate control (Larsen et al. 2022 (Nunataryuk Deliverable Report 9.4)).

Culture & language: Increased permafrost thaw causes impacts on livelihoods and subsistence, heritage and identity, if, for example, food sources change and intergenerational knowledge transfer is threatened.

Health & wellbeing: Impacts on physical and mental health and wellbeing include, for example, higher potentials for injuries and greater insecurity in terms of safe food consumption.

Costs & economy: Repairs and new equipment, a higher reliance on store-bought food, physical protective measures and other necessary adaptation measures financially impact communities, families and individuals.

Ecosystem (functioning): Disruptions and changes, such as changing nutrient fluxes, bio-accumulation of mercury and outbreaks of anthrax disease, cause concerns about the normal functioning of ecosystems.

Recreation & being in nature: Recreational activities and being in nature is adversely affected, for example, by changes in navigable water and terrestrial paths and more difficult access to camps.

Planning & fate control: Planning and fate control are impacted by, for example, the potential loss of connectivity and supply irregularities. The need for new water and food sources may arise.

Adaptation and mitigation actions can apply to either the physical processes involved, the key hazards or to the consequence domains of permafrost thaw. The following section presents a brief overview of results of a survey on communities' perceptions of permafrost thaw. It describes results that are relevant specifically for questions of adaptation.

5. Results from survey on adaptation strategies

A survey on community perceptions of permafrost thaw was carried out between 2019 and 2020 in Aklavik (Northwest Territories, Canada), Longyearbyen (Svalbard, Norway), and Qeqertarsuaq (Qeqertalik Municipality, Greenland). The survey was translated into English, Greenlandic, Danish and Norwegian and was carried out using snowball sampling. Local field assistants were hired in Aklavik and Qeqertarsuaq, who were acquainted with the field. In total, 237 participants took the survey, meaning 11% of the population above 18 years old in Aklavik, 15% in Qeqertarsuaq, and 4% in Longyearbyen – with a relatively even distribution across gender and age groups. The results were published in several scientific publications, namely: Ramage et al. (2022), Timlin et al. (2022a, 2022b), and they were discussed in the Nunataryuk Deliverable Report 7.5 (Ramage et al. 2020). Furthermore, in early 2023 the same survey with some minor adjustments was conducted in Ilulissat, Greenland. We also briefly report on those results in the following.

Permafrost zones

Map 1: Location of the three focus communities located within the Arctic Circumpolar Permafrost Region (Ramage et al. 2022). Map by Nordregio.

Four questions of the survey dealt specifically with adaptive capacity in the three communities. These were: 1) In which of these domains is there the strongest need to adapt to thawing of the frozen ground in order to facilitate day to day activities? 2) In which ways do you think your community is best prepared to adapt to the thawing of the frozen ground? 3) Do you feel that enough is being done to adapt or face the impacts related to thawing of the frozen ground? 4) Do you feel empowered to face these changes? In what follows, we present the results of these questions for each community separately.

5.1. Longyearbyen, Svalbard

In Longyearbyen, a total of 84 responses were gathered between August 2019 and January 2020. More than 70 of the answers were collected using a printed paper version, the rest were answered online. The respondents were either interviewed directly by the researcher or filled out the survey which was later collected. The researcher carrying out and analyzing the survey is a native Norwegian speaker and speaks English. She informed all participants about the project, how the data would be used, and that participation is voluntary before they answered the survey. The respondents were contacted by going from door to door, whereby the streets were chosen randomly, and through personal contacts. The face-to-face data gathering resulted in qualitative data in addition to the survey data, which complement the latter, adding context and depth.

Housing is clearly considered the domain in which there is the strongest need to adapt to permafrost thaw, with other domains such as traditional knowledge or hunting and fishing, not considered important in this regard (Fig. 1).

Housing is also the domain in which the community is perceived to be best prepared to adapt to permafrost thaw, according to the respondents. However, here 10 of the 18 respondents that

indicated “other” said that they did not know, and several respondents remarked that the question was difficult to understand. One respondent remarked “In all domains, the whole society has to adapt.” (Fig. 2)

The Longyearbyen respondents feel that the community and individuals are doing enough or somewhat enough to adapt to the effects of permafrost thaw. By the global community and national authorities, however, the dominant view is that not enough is being done. (Fig. 3)

More than a third of the respondents feel empowered to face the changes related to permafrost thaw affecting Longyearbyen, whereas almost a fourth do not. 41% feel somewhat empowered to face them. (Fig. 4)

5.2. Aklavik, NWT Canada

In Aklavik we received a total of 53 responses (23 male, 30 female and 31 respondents were at the time above the age of 45 years) to the survey, which was carried out with the help of two research assistants. Traditional (Indigenous) knowledge and subsistence activities (hunting, fishing etc.) are considered the domains in which there is the strongest need to adapt to permafrost thaw, while domains such as mobility and health are not considered important in this regard.

In which of these domains is there the strongest need to adapt to thawing of the frozen ground in order to facilitate day to day activities?

Interestingly, similar to the results from Longyearbyen related to housing, traditional knowledge is also the domain in which Aklavik is perceived to be best prepared to adapt to permafrost thaw, according to the respondents. Hunting and fishing activities come (albeit far behind) in second place. A reason why these two domains were singled out both as the ones where most adaptation is needed and where the community is best prepared may be because traditional (Indigenous) knowledge and subsistence are extremely important to community resilience. Thus, they need to be adapted to face local impacts of climate change and at the same time, if Indigenous knowledge and subsistence activities are doing well, they contribute significantly to overall wellbeing.

In which ways do you think your community is best prepared to adapt to thawing of the frozen ground?

Most Aklavik respondents feel that the community, local and regional (as well as national) authorities (and the global community) are doing enough or somewhat enough to adapt to the effects of permafrost thaw. Interestingly however, the dominant view is that only somewhat or not enough is being done by individuals.

More than two thirds of the respondents feel at least somewhat empowered to face the changes related to permafrost thaw affecting Aklavik, whereas 22% do not.

5.3. Qeqertarsuaq, Disko Bay, West Greenland

Survey results from Qeqertarsuaq were presented in Nunataryuk Deliverable Report 7.5 (Ramage et al. 2020; also in Ramage et al. 2022) but here we present a few quick results from those reports for purposes of overall discussion in this report. The survey results (see Nunataryuk Deliverable Report 7.5 ((Ramage et al. 2020)) show that most respondents find that adaptation measures should focus on mobility (34%), health (18%), and housing (18%). Further, mobility in Qeqertarsuaq is seen as the area with the highest adaptation need, but not an area the participants feel prepared for. Also, respondents feel the community (76%), local authorities (74%), individuals (68%) and national authorities (64%) are not doing enough to face the impacts related to permafrost thaw. As in the case of Aklavik, results show that respondents find that the adaptation responsibility is placed on the individual and community (for more details see Nunataryuk Deliverable Report 7.5 (Ramage et al. 2020); and Ramage et al. 2022).

5.4. Ilulissat, Disko Bay, West Greenland

A survey with 4 similar questions on adaptation was also conducted in Ilulissat, Disko Bay, in January 2023. Survey responses were received from 22 females og 31 males: a total of 53 responses from a broad range of stakeholders. Of the 22 females, 5 females were in the age group 18-30; 4 in the age group 31-45; 8 in the age group 46-60; and 5 in the age group above 60. Of the 31 males, 4 males were in the age group 18-30; 8 in the age group 31-45; 10 in the age group 46-60; and 9 in the age group above 60.

The first question asked was: In your view in which of the following areas is there the strongest need to adapt to thawing of the frozen ground to facilitate day to day activities? (Fig. 1). By far the largest number of respondents (79.2%) answered “Infrastructure (roads, building environment), which was followed by “Housing” (58.5%), “Mobility/Transportation” (39.6%), and Financial Planning (30.2%). Hunting/fishing activities (20.7%), and Health (16.9%) were also seen as important by many, whereas only a smaller number of respondents answered Traditional Knowledge (13.2%), Work Related Processes (13.2%), and Other (7.5%).

The survey revealed several interesting gender differences: Females find Health (27.3%) more important than males, with only 9.7% of male responding that Health is the area with the strongest need to adapt. Similarly, while 77.3% of female respondents found Housing to be the most important area to adapt, the share of male respondents is significantly lower at 45.2%. About twice as many females as males responded Traditional Knowledge (18.2% of females) versus only 9.7% for males, and similarly for Work Related Processes with 18.2% of females finding this to be an important area to adapt versus only 9.7% of males. Financial Planning and Mobility was similar across females and males, whereas males find infrastructure (83.9%) a more important area for adaptation than females (72.7%).

The second question asked was: In which of these areas do you think your community is best prepared to adapt to thawing of the frozen ground? (Fig. 2). Many respondents found Traditional Knowledge (28.3%), Mobility (22.6%), Infrastructure (20.8%), and Housing (20.8%) the areas where the community is best prepared to adapt to permafrost thaw. On the other hand, only 7.5% found the community well prepared in terms of Financial Planning, and 15.1% in Health. 18.9% of the respondents found work-related processes to be an area where the community was well prepared. 9.4% responded "Other". Notable gender differences exist: the biggest differences between male and female responses were in Health (22.7% of females vs 9.7% of males); Financial Planning (13.6% of females vs 3.2% of males); and Infrastructure (27.3% of females vs 16.1% of males). In contrast, males perceived better preparedness in Traditional Knowledge and Housing than females, with 32.2% of males responding that Traditional Knowledge is the area best prepared to adapt vs 22.7% of females; and for Housing, 19.4% of males vs 22.7% of females.

In the third survey question (Fig. 3) we asked the respondents whether they feel that enough is being done by individuals, community, local authorities, national authorities, global community (Arctic Council, United Nations etc.) to adapt or face the impacts related to thawing of the frozen ground. 24.5% of the respondents answered that they feel enough is being done by the global community; 22.6% answered “by local authorities”; 20.8% (national authorities), by individuals (18.9%), and by the community (15.1%). However, the results also revealed important gender differences in the responses: 22.7% of females find that the Community is doing enough, compared to only 9.7% of males. 25.8% of males find that enough is being done at the National level, compared to only 13.6% of females.

In our final survey question (Fig. 4), we asked respondents whether they feel empowered to face the changes caused by permafrost thaw. 20.8% of respondents answered “Yes”; 26.4% answered “No”, while a total of 35.8% answered “somewhat”. A smaller number of respondents answered “I don’t know” (11.3%). There were some important gender differences in the responses: whereas responses by females were evenly distributed on the 4 options, a total of 45% of males answered “somewhat”, 19% answered “No”, and 29% answered “Yes”, while only 3.2% answered “I don’t know”. The biggest gender difference was found where 45% of males responded that they feel somewhat empowered to face the changes caused by permafrost thaw, compared to only 22.7% of the females. And while only 3.2% of males answered that they don’t know if they feel empowered, 22.7 % of females answered that they don’t know, indicating that males overall feel more empowered to face the changes.

5.5. Summary of survey results

Overall, survey results from all case study regions suggest similarities and differences in local perceptions of areas to adapt and feelings of empowerment to adapt:

Survey results from Longyearbyen and Aklavik suggest that the area with the perceived strongest need to adapt by locals is also the area with the strongest perceived preparedness to adapt (which area this is differs between the field sites). In Longyearbyen responses show that the area with the strongest perceived need to adapt and the area with the perceived best preparedness to adapt is “housing”, whereas in Aklavik, most of the respondents answered “Traditional knowledge” – as the area with both strongest need, and best preparedness. In Ilulissat on the other hand, where the survey also included “Infrastructure” as a possible survey answer, most respondents answered that the area with the strongest need to adapt is “Infrastructure (roads, building environment)”, while

the best preparedness is perceived to be in “Traditional Knowledge” followed by “Mobility and Infrastructure”. Thus, “Traditional Knowledge” is perceived by locals in both Aklavik and Ilulissat to be the area with the best preparedness to adapt to permafrost thaw.

Differences also exist in what level locals feel enough is being done to adapt or face the impacts related to permafrost thaw. In Longyearbyen respondents feel that the community and individuals are doing enough or somewhat enough to adapt to the effects of permafrost thaw. However, the dominant view is that not enough is being done the global community and national authorities. In the case of Aklavik however most respondents feel that the community, local and regional (as well as national) authorities (and the global community) are doing enough or somewhat enough to adapt to the effects of permafrost thaw. While respondents in Longyearbyen find that enough is being done by individuals, the dominant view in Aklavik is that only somewhat or not enough is being done by individuals. Similarly, in the case of Ilulissat the level with the lowest response rate in terms of at what level enough is being done to adapt to permafrost thaw is at the community and individual level, whereas a larger share of respondents find that enough is being done by the global community, followed by the local and national authorities. However, the results also reveal important gender differences in the responses in Ilulissat, with more than one-fifth of females finding that the Community is doing enough, compared to just below 10% of males. Whereas a large share of males find that enough is being done at the National level, the share of women who feel similarly is only about half that.

Finally, on the question of feeling empowered to tackle changes caused by permafrost thaw important differences exist between the case regions: In the case of Ilulissat more respondents feel they are not empowered to face the changes caused by permafrost thaw as opposed to empowered, but the most frequent response was a feeling of being somewhat empowered. These answers are similar to the case of Aklavik, while in the case of Longyearbyen the most frequent response was feeling empowered or somewhat empowered. At the same time, males in Ilulissat feel more empowered than females to face the changes; and for both males and females, respondents in the age group 46+ feel more empowered than others to face the changes.

6. Case studies

In the following, we present results from the qualitative fieldwork carried out in the three study regions.

6.1. Longyearbyen, Svalbard

Longyearbyen is located on the Western coast of the high-Arctic archipelago of Svalbard, part of the Kingdom of Norway. Svalbard never had an indigenous population, and its settlements developed as coal mining towns. Longyearbyen (ca. 2600 inhabitants) is the archipelago’s largest settlement. And its administrative center. The former coal mining company town is at the tail end of an economic restructuring, and tourism and the related service industry, in addition to research

and higher education, constitute its main economic pillars today (Sokolíčková, Meyer & Vlachov 2022). Longyearbyen is a highly modern, “urban village”, at the same time geographically remote and well-connected to the Norwegian mainland via its airport. Its population is transient, young and increasingly international, with around 30% of the population from outside Norway.

Svalbard is experiencing severe climatic changes (Hanssen-Bauer et al. 2019): Temperatures have risen 4 degrees celcius since 1971, which is five times faster than the global average. Permafrost on Svalbard is continuous, with thickness ranging from a few meters along the coast to up to 500 meters in highland areas (Christiansen et al. 2019). Permafrost temperatures on Svalbard have increased in recent years, and an increase of the active layer has been observed at some sites (Hanssen-Bauer et al. 2019). Under high emission scenarios, near-surface permafrost in coastal and low-lying areas is projected to thaw before the end of the century (ibid.). The climate profile for Longyearbyen (Norsk Klimaservicesenter 2019) projects that air temperature will continue to increase, as will annual precipitation. Thawing of the upper layers of permafrost is expected, as are more frequent events with strong precipitation, and more rain in winter. Increased precipitation and snow and glacier melt will result in more flooding, and river and coastal erosion are predicted. There will furthermore be an increase in snow and slush avalanches in coming years, and a thicker active permafrost layer in combination with more frequent rain events result in unstable slopes, increasing the risk for landslides and debris flows. Longyearbyen is often depicted as either a climate change victim or a showcase of technological solutions in the face of change (Meyer & Sokolíčková, forthcoming): In response to natural hazards such as snow avalanches, landslides, and infrastructural challenges due to permafrost thaw and coastal erosion, the town is adapting by producing environmental knowledge, reconfiguring the urban landscape, and developing technical protection measures (Meyer 2022).

6.1.1. Methods

The qualitative data from Longyearbyen was gathered throughout a long-term ethnographic fieldwork spanning from 2018 to 2022. During this time the researcher was living in Longyearbyen for a total of 20 months, working in different but related projects. Qualitative data was gathered through participant observation, informal ethnographic interviews, semi-structured interviews including expert interviews, and “netnography”, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. In 67 interviews, spanning from 10 minutes to three hours, permafrost was mentioned or explicitly discussed, in addition to numerous informal conversations and participant observation at relevant events. The interviews were mostly in Norwegian and English, and some in German and Spanish

In addition to the qualitative data, a survey about the social impacts of permafrost thaw was conducted in Longyearbyen, as in other field sites. A total of 84 responses were gathered between August 2019 and January 2020. More than 70 of the answers were collected using a printed paper version, the rest were answered online. The respondents were either interviewed directly by the researcher, or filled out the survey which was later collected. The researcher carrying out and also analyzing the survey is a native Norwegian speaker and also speaks English. She informed all participants about the project, how the data would be used, and that participation is voluntary

before they answered the survey. The respondents were contacted by going from door to door, whereby the streets were chosen randomly, and through personal contacts. The face-to-face data gathering resulted in qualitative data in addition to the survey data, which complement the latter, adding context and depth.

6.1.2. Description of results and discussion

“Adaptation is absolutely necessary.” Adaptation to permafrost thaw is in Longyearbyen considered as necessary, both by professionals and non-professionals. Adaptation is generally considered possible, as illustrated by the following interview quote: “The main problem is in regard to buildings and infrastructure, as the buildings move and destabilize when the permafrost thaws. But we can easily adapt to this - we just have to pile the piles further down, or fundament them on bedrock, this was not done before which is why many buildings struggle today. So adaptation is possible.” This also reflects the view of planners, technical staff at LL, engineers, and scientists I interviewed in Longyearbyen (Meyer 2022). The general attitude is that engineering solutions to deal with permafrost thaw exist, and planners think it’s possible to build in Longyearbyen in the future. Furthermore, adaptation to permafrost thaw is considered a public responsibility. Permafrost thaw is by most participants perceived as a societal rather than a personal risk, and, correspondingly, the survey and the interviews indicate that people in Longyearbyen do not consider adaptation to permafrost thaw a task of individuals, but rather the task of the state, authorities, or the employer. Several participants indicated that an unspecified “we” is the actor that is adapting or should adapt. Other participants pointed to “society” as the adapting actor. Still others pointed to unspecified “others” (as opposed to “we”): “It is not the responsibility of the local community.” Interestingly, none of the participants indicated that they personally were adapting actors, except for when talking about changing hiking routes and trails. In Longyearbyen, people generally feel that enough or somewhat enough is being done by the community to adapt to permafrost thaw, but they also expressed that the global community and national authorities are not contributing enough.

The key risk people mostly associate with permafrost thaw in Longyearbyen are impacts on the built environment (housing and infrastructure), and housing is also clearly considered the domain in which there is the strongest need to adapt to permafrost thaw and the domain towards which most attention and resources are directed in terms of adaptation. Numerous engineering adaptation measures exist and are applied in this regard (see Appendix). Another key risk related to permafrost thaw in Longyearbyen are environmental risks, i.e. challenges associated with changes in the physical environment, most notably landslides and avalanches. Risks to physical and mental health as well as safety problems as a result of natural hazards such as landslides is a main concern related to permafrost thaw. The past years (the avalanches in 2015 and 2016 were catalysts of action in this domain) there has been high emphasis on natural hazards in Longyearbyen and safety through adaptation has been a top political priority (Meyer 2022). Another perceived key risk related to human and animal health is the release of contaminants due to permafrost thaw. In this domain adaptations include to clean up old land fillings, but challenges remain. In the domain of water

and food security, people express concern for how permafrost thaw can impact the local freshwater reserve. The water reserve in winter comes from a dam called *Isdammen*, literally the ice dam: the water is dammed up, and this dam is held together by permafrost. The adaptation measures to deal with this challenge is to put on new masses, but the risk of this dam breaking due to thawing permafrost remains, according to experts. In the domain of culture and recreation, the biggest concern are permafrost thaw impacts on cultural heritage in terms of structural destabilization, as well as hillside and coastal erosion. There are different ways to adapt cultural heritage on Svalbard to permafrost thaw, including exchanging and building new foundations of buildings and mining infrastructure, and currently there are several ongoing research projects to address this challenge. Thus, technical solutions to adapt cultural heritage structures to permafrost thaw exist. However, these often conflict with heritage values such as historical authenticity, if the technical interventions alter the structure, creating dilemmas for cultural heritage management (Sinitsyn et al. 2022). In fact, heritage management on Svalbard in many cases prevents technical adaptations of cultural heritage structures, often to the frustration of local authorities, owners of cultural heritage, and inhabitants. Another issue of concern in the domain of culture and recreation are eroding hillsides and other impacts on hiking trails. People adapt to this by changing their routes.

Most research participants in Longyearbyen talked about adaptations in the physical realm, related to the built environment: foundations, piles, piling depth. Permafrost thaw is often perceived as a physical challenge that can be dealt with by physical means (Meyer 2022). However, people also talked about a different, more challenging, approach to adaptation: adaptation in the sense of social transformation. To one participant, dealing with climate change would mean to make Longyearbyen more sustainable (however without specifying what that would entail): “Longyearbyen is not very sustainable, that should be a place to start, to make the town more sustainable.” Another participant pointed to Longyearbyen’s dependence on coal for energy and a change of lifestyle as ways to act in the face of change: “We are facing changes here every day, but not doing anything. People are living just like before, nobody is changing their lifestyle. We are still heating with coal.” Mitigation in terms of transitioning towards a more sustainable society is generally perceived as the greater challenge, and people express concern that not enough is being done in this regard.

The knowledge base for adaptation to permafrost thaw is relatively high in Longyearbyen. The town is a hub for Arctic science, including permafrost and climate change research. There is a growing body of publicly available research and reports about environmental conditions on Svalbard and in Longyearbyen, and research on how climate change impacts this environment has become an important industry on Svalbard. Even though conventional science continues to be seen as the main base for decision making and planning in Longyearbyen, there is an increase in projects on environmental changes that include local actors such as the local government or the Governor as partners, to ensure local relevance of the research, and that draw on a more diversified and participatory way of knowledge making. There is collaboration between the local government and The University Centre in Svalbard (UNIS), and a good dialogue between members of both institutions, especially regarding permafrost. It was still pointed out by some interview partners

that there is room for improvement of such collaboration and that gaps between research and practice persist. Furthermore, the private building and construction sector is not very much integrated in this knowledge exchange, and neither are knowledge holders outside of institutions, such as retired or former employees of the local government or the mining company Store Norske, responsible for running the town before the installment of the local government.

In interviews and conversations with local inhabitants, several challenges to adaptation were identified. While it is technically feasible to adapt to permafrost thaw according to the interview partners, and the engineering solutions to deal with this challenge exist, challenges to adaptation are rather economic and political. As expressed by one interview participant: “Most can be solved technically, but it is the economy it depends on, and the priorities regarding what is important for society.” The high costs involved with adapting to changing climate and building according to the climate projections were emphasized in many interviews: “It is very difficult, but most can be solved, but it is the costs, it is expensive, it is very expensive.” Planners and engineers are particularly concerned about the future costs involved with adapting existing infrastructure and buildings to permafrost thaw, which will require new foundations for much of the existing built environment. As a member of the administrative staff of the local government told me, the institution now finds itself in a situation where different environmental pressures require action simultaneously, and the sum of several projects become a challenge:

The problem occurs when a small community gets many such pots. When we first get a bill down at the river and the a bill up here in the slopes, and the a bill for securing the energy station, and then some millions because we’re demolishing our houses and build new ones, and suddenly all these portions involved with the transformation become so big that a small community cannot carry it. So it is the sum of all these changes that make us struggle. [...] One has to understand that if we want to adapt, then there are many sums. [...] And we have to look at this in total, not separately, but as a whole.

In this regard, it was mentioned by several participants that the agency of the local government is limited by the fact that it does not receive incomes from taxes, but is directly reliant on yearly state transfers, which in some cases also complicates long-term planning. According to the interview partners, the ability to adapt Longyearbyen to a changing environment ultimately depends on the Norwegian state’s willingness to invest in the town: “It is the state that decides if we will adapt in the future. If Longyearbyen will exist a hundred years from now.” From today’s viewpoint, there are reasons to assume that Norway’s politics of presence (Pedersen 2017) on Svalbard will ensure the necessary investments for adapting the town to a changing environment on 78 degrees North. The high turnover of the population in Longyearbyen is another main challenge for adaptation. Long-term place attachment is often emphasized as crucial for communities’ capacity to deal with environmental changes, as this entails intimate environmental knowledge and skills (Amundsen 2015). In Longyearbyen, however, there is a lack of memories, observations, and stories about past events that could inform current risk assessments and documentations of change: “It [the turnover] has been really problematic. Most people are here just a couple of years. [...] It is no doubt a challenge that collective memory is that short”, an interview partner explained. Another related challenge is that people are typically occupying positions in Longyearbyen only for a short time.

As people go in and out of positions, knowledge gets lost: “Of course a lot slips away when there is that much turnover”, a planner in the local government told me. Participants from different sectors explained that it typically takes at least a year before people are acquainted with their job and the specific challenges and topics. A planner explained that “when we get new people, they won’t have the competences before after a while, so it is vulnerable in that sense”. A participant working in the local government added another nuance:

What is maybe even scarier, is political memory. On the mainland you often have a solid political memory, people are sitting in the local government for ages, they are passionate about their parish and have their agenda, right, they are there with a purpose [...]. We have a big turnover in politics, and that means that we have neither administrative memory nor political memory and the combination of those two is what makes this scary.

The interviews suggest that this is a challenge in all sectors: Administration, research, politics, consultancy, with the exception of parts of the building and construction sector. Furthermore, climate change, which makes it harder to plan, and introduces uncertainties, was mentioned as a challenge to adaptation.

In general, people consider mitigation as being the greater challenge, as illustrated by this interview quote: “Longyearbyen is not very sustainable, that should be a place to start, to make the town more sustainable”, and people express that not enough is being done to mitigate climate change.

6.2. Beaufort Sea Area and Mackenzie River Delta, Canada

The Canadian case study examines four communities situated in the Northwest Territories, either within or near the Mackenzie Delta, located in the western Arctic region of Canada. Inuvik has a population of approximately 3,500 and is situated on the East Channel of the Mackenzie River. The town embraces its Inuvialuit and Gwich'in cultural heritage while accommodating diverse backgrounds. It provides essential amenities for the larger region, such as schools, healthcare facilities, and recreational opportunities, while serving as a gateway to the Inuvik-Tuktoyaktuk Highway. Aklavik is a small community with a population of approximately 600 residents. The town, located on the banks of the Peel River, is predominantly inhabited by Gwich'in First Nation and Inuvialuit people. It is reachable from Inuvik by airplane or boat during late spring, summer and early fall and by ice road during the winter season. Tuktoyaktuk, an Arctic coastal community, is home to around 900 residents, primarily consisting of Inuvialuit people. Accessible primarily by air and sea, Tuktoyaktuk can also be reached by land through the Inuvik-Tuktoyaktuk Highway, providing a vital lifeline for transportation and connecting the town to the rest of the NWT. This remote community serves as a significant research site for studying the effects of permafrost thaw, coastal erosion, and the broader impacts of climate change in the Arctic. Fort McPherson has a population of approximately 800 residents and is also situated along the Peel River, and the home of mainly Gwich'in First Nation citizens. The town can be reached primarily by air and land routes, notably the Dempster Highway connecting the Mackenzie River Delta Region to Southern Canada.

Alongside a temperature increase exceeding two degrees Celsius between the mid-20th century and 2016 (Bush & Lemmen 2019), several changes have occurred, including increased rainfall and humidity, diminished snow and ice levels (Box et al. 2019), glacial melting (Asong et al. 2020), shifting wind patterns (Wesche & Chan 2010), as well as heightened occurrences of storms (Ford et al. 2018) and flooding (Worden et al. 2020). Moreover, these changes have led to coastal and river bank erosion (Wesche & Chan 2010, Worden et al. 2020), along with subsidence and slumping caused by permafrost thaw, impacting the predominantly Inuvialuit and Gwich'in First Nation population. These alterations pose risks to infrastructure, health and wellbeing, mobility, and the security of supplies, food, and water (Irrgang et al. 2019, Lantz & Kokelj 2008, Lantz & Turner 2015, Ramage et al. 2016).

6.2.1. Methods

The qualitative data from the Mackenzie River Delta and Beaufort Sea Area was gathered primarily throughout long-term ethnographic fieldwork between September 2022 through to February 2023. During this time the researcher was living in Inuvik and conducted research visits to Aklavik, Fort McPherson, and Tuktoyaktuk. Prior to that, in March 2019, a one-week project introduction was carried out in Inuvik and Aklavik, engaging multiple stakeholders including representatives from the Inuvialuit Regional Corporation and the Gwich'in Tribal Council.

From 2019 to 2022, a combination of online interviews, literature review, and workshops with Nunataryuk scientists and Indigenous organizations in Aklavik and Tuktoyaktuk took place. This included 24 weeks of fieldwork starting in mid-September 2022, where expert interviews with local organizations, regional engineering, heritage, and permafrost experts were conducted. Field visits were made to various sites along the Dempster Highway, Inuvik-Tuktoyaktuk Highway, and the Mackenzie River channel connecting Inuvik and Aklavik. Additionally, qualitative semi-structured life-history and land-use interviews were conducted with 24 Indigenous knowledge holders (fluent in English), lasting an average of 1 to 1.5 hours.

The “Permafrost Days 2023” (UARctic transdisciplinary workshops) were a series of events organized by Susanna Gartler between the 7th to 9th of February in Inuvik and Aklavik. They brought together visiting scientists with local stakeholders to gather data, and to discuss the relevance and applicability of scientific results with the communities of Inuvik, Aklavik and Tuktoyaktuk. The researcher organized two workshops, one each in Inuvik and Aklavik, which were attended by a large variety of representatives of local and regional organizations. These included the AHTC, the THTC, the Gwich'in Tribal Council (Department of Lands and Resources), the Gwich'in Development Corporation, the Aurora Research Institute, the NWT Department of Infrastructure and the Department of Natural Resources, the Hamlet of Inuvik, the Inuvik Greenhouse, the NWT Geological Survey, the Inuvialuit Regional Corporation and Parks Canada. In this group we discussed in depth key hazards, socio-economic and health-related consequences, indicators of permafrost thaw impacts as well as adaptation measures.

Qualitative data was thus gathered through participant observation, informal ethnographic interviews, and semi-structured interviews including expert interviews as well as through the

workshops in February 2023. In addition to the qualitative data, a survey about the social impacts of permafrost thaw was conducted in Aklavik, as in other field sites (see previous section of this report). A total of 53 responses were gathered. The research assistants informed all participants about the project, how the data would be used, and that participation is voluntary before they answered the survey. The respondents were contacted by going from door to door, whereby the streets were chosen randomly, and through personal contacts. The face-to-face data gathering resulted in qualitative data in addition to the survey data, which complement the latter, adding context and depth.

6.2.2. Description of results

“We have no choice but to adapt”: Adaptation to permafrost thaw is in the Mackenzie River Delta and Beaufort Sea Area considered as unavoidable and necessary, by all stakeholders. There is very little most respondents felt that they could do to mitigate global warming, while rising temperatures were mentioned by all respondents as a visible sign of environmental changes. Since many interviews were conducted during fall 2022 and cold temperatures were still far from arriving in the area at that point in time, a typical statement was: “We are still boating today! Normally we would already be driving our skiddoos!” Generally speaking, monitoring was seen by many respondents as an important adaptation tool – not only of erosion for example, but also of changes along roads – and important to be able to meet challenges related to permafrost thaw.

Most adaptation and mitigation measures are applicable in the domain of infrastructure. The key risk people mostly associated with permafrost thaw in the Mackenzie River Delta and Beaufort Sea Region is coastal and river bank erosion. Mitigation measures include preventing permafrost thaw along river shoreline by cutting down large trees, putting brush against shore, and flood control measures along the sea shore, for example. Adaptation measures include moving cabins and houses, i.e., from the so-called spit in Tuktoyaktuk to Reindeer Point, or moving cabins further away from river shores: “My camp was closer to the bank last year. In preparation for the big flood that we were expecting, I had to cut brush behind my camp, lots of brush. And then I had to buy beams to go underneath my house. Get chains and come-alongs and straps. And I had to get my house ready and then we hooked it up. And then we pulled it back, because the ground was falling (the river shoreline was eroding). My cabin just had enough land beside it for a skiddoo to go by it, that's how close it got.” Foundation upgrades and using new foundations in construction are other common adaptation measures. Further actions that are being taken include devising new ways of building on changing conditions, developing new technologies and/or using innovative materials, modifying vegetation to stabilize ground, and drawing on Indigenous knowledge and building techniques and technologies. Collective, reciprocal help amongst community members was also mentioned several times as a factor adding to adaptive capacity, especially within the Indigenous communities: „We are a tight-knit community. If someone needs help, there are always people there to jump in. Challenges in this domain are a lack of knowledge (not every cabin owner knows where to place their cabins, for example, so they remain safe from river bank erosion), lack of manpower and lack of support for innovation. Moreover, effective intergenerational knowledge

transfer, especially also intergenerational Indigenous knowledge transfer is threatened by rapidly changing conditions and the introduction of new technologies.

In terms of health and wellbeing, communication was mentioned as being important and several respondents reported being more careful when driving across tundra today, mainly because of soft ground in which you may get stuck in (causing respondents to compare this to “quicksand”). Moreover, increased use of safety tools such as safety kits and life-jackets, reducing search & rescue times and offering (boat) safety training are actions taken to adapt to changing and more dangerous circumstances. Mental health concerns were a concern especially for respondents who experienced an abrupt thaw/erosion event in their vicinity recently. For example, one respondent, whose cabin is located very close to an area where a large piece of river bank more than 100 hundred meters wide suddenly broke off during the summer of 2022, voiced concerns about the safety of her cabin, and commented on the stress related to the uncertainty surrounding such large abrupt erosion, and other thaw events. Communication was mentioned as being key to reducing uncertainty and adapting to more unstable and unpredictable conditions: “I’m going to put up a cell phone booster. So then at least I could have that for communication. I have a mobile radio as well. Lots of cabin owners moved over to the marine radios.”

When it comes to material wellbeing and costs, many respondents commented on the increase in costs driven by inflation, and that adapting to changes can be very costly. Funding for „on the land“ subsistence activities is available to some extent, and in some instances certain losses are insured. However, rising costs of living were clearly indicated as a challenge, not only in relation to climate change adaptation but to life in general, by most respondents. Moreover, it was mentioned that living off the land is expensive enough as it is, thus additional strains by increased permafrost thaw and it’s impacts are harder to meet financially.

Cultural vitality is negatively affected because time and resources are taken away by necessary adaptation measures: As an example, instead of being able to go out hunting and fishing, people need to relocate their houses or cabins. At the same time Indigenous knowledge is seen as an important resource for adaptation. For example, terminology workshops including outreach products are produced for translation of scientific terms regarding climate changes in to Indigenous languages. One example of challenges concerning cultural heritage and permafrost thaw is the so-called Igloo Church in Inuvik, which experienced problems with permafrost thaw due to a construction error during maintenance work. At one point the floor of the building dropped significantly and had to be re-elevated manually. The construction error was then identified and rectified and the Aurora Research Institute is monitoring ground temperatures underneath the building, which is considered part of the local heritage. Several Indigenous heritage sites at risk from coastal erosion are also being monitored by cultural heritage specialists of the GNWT.

In terms of water and food security, several adaptation measures were reported. For example, hunters would take more time to find moose who hide better behind higher willows – or they would invest more time to move around large thaw slumps on their hunting trips. Thus, in addition to time investments, travel routes are modified by land users to account for changing ground and vegetation conditions. Changing river depths were mentioned several times also, with respondents

explaining that they would use different routes if a certain channel became too shallow, for example. One respondent mentioned that, since subsistence is negatively impacted by increased permafrost thaw, planning for increased protection of subsistence harvest rights and ecosystem rights is becoming more important: „If our subsistence harvest is going to be endangered by climate change, then we have to start working on protecting those rights and the animals on our own.“

Local, regional and national entities plan for permafrost thaw induced changes, by putting forth strategic plans (see for example the NWT Climate Change Strategic Plan, the ISR Climate Change Strategy, the Tetl'it Gwich'in Climate Change Adaptation Plan, the Gwichya Gwich'in Climate Change Adaptation Planning Project), action maps (i.e., the Inuvialuit Settlement Region Climate Change Action Map), programs such as the Inuvialuit Climate Watch Program, hazard maps (i.e., the Aurora College Digital Hazard Maps of Landslides) and emergency preparedness plans. Long-term planning for flood control based on scientific evaluations of coastal erosion, for example, and planning for moving houses eventually, can take place long before the need actually arises. Challenges include that communities feel that there has been a lot of research but not enough consequent, research-based actions taken. At the same time the need for research is acknowledged. One respondent expressed the need for large-scale solutions, f.e. the use of certain plants to stabilize the ground, including their timely execution. The following quote exemplifies the prevalent understanding that despite much research, by far not enough is being done: „We need action! We had researchers for years and years and years, who come up here. Enough of this. We need help!”

For obvious reasons, adaptation actions in terms of Recreation and Being in Nature overlap to some extent with the actions described in the paragraph on food security. In addition, adaptation actions can include choosing different recreational spaces if a particular (hiking) trail is closed, for example – or changing one’s time of vacation if a road is closed due to landslides. On Qikiqtaruk (Herschel Island) cruise-ship tourists are asked to either stay on the gravel shore or to spread out instead of walking in single lines on Herschel Island, because otherwise the vegetation cover of the increasingly wet tundra gets disturbed significantly along the walking trails.

In terms of mobility (travel and transportation) respondents reported being more careful and attentive while travelling across the land, in order to avoid areas of soft ground that were likened to “quick sand” or in order to avoid large slumps. As mentioned in the sections above, travel and hunting routes and times are also adapted to changing circumstances. The Dempster Highway and Inuvik- Tuktoyaktuk Highway (ITH) represent the most important road connections in the area. Municipalities, such as Inuvik and Tuktoyaktuk collaborate with scientists of the NWT and ARI to monitor changes along these roadways. The Joint Secretariat established a monitoring program specifically for the ITH, where all changes and impacts along the highway (whether permafrost related or other impacts of the road on the surrounding ecosystems) are monitored throughout most of the year, except during winter.

Most research participants in the Mackenzie River Delta and Beaufort Sea Area were not particularly concerned about energy supply and needs for adaptation in that regard. Generally

speaking, risks to energy supply could result from infrastructure failure, such as instability of electricity poles or instability of energy supply facilities – and from flooding or erosion. At the same time a number of new energy projects are currently being developed or are under construction, such as a wind turbine and solar panels near Inuvik, as well as natural gas projects spearheaded by the Inuvialuit Regional Corporation, which aim to utilize old gas wells near Tuktoyaktuk. In terms of mitigation and the reduction of emissions in people’s private lives there is very little discussion, however some participants commented on for example not letting cars run outdoors during winter time.

Education and training are seen as important components of adaptation and mitigation actions. Some Elders commented on the fact that Youth can teach older generations about the use of new technology that can help with navigating on the land. In turn, Elders pass on their knowledge about safely being on the land to Youth. However, significant challenges are posed to effective intergenerational knowledge transfer today, which is threatened by increasingly changing and unpredictable conditions, meaning that (some) Indigenous and local knowledge about for example weather and ground conditions has become unreliable. Important issues such as (changing conditions for) caribou hunting, polar bears, fish or an increasing beaver population are being tackled by locally organized workshops and meetings targeting (Indigenous) land users as well as the general population. Thus, the need to educate and train locally and to ensure successful science communication to the local population is acknowledged and tackled actively by local organizations.

6.2.3. Discussion

Climate change adaptation has been examined in the Inuvialuit Settlement Region/Beaufort Sea Region primarily through interviews, analysis of academic literature, government bodies’ reports and adaptation plans, and a survey. The research finds that there is high awareness of the need for adaptation on the side of regulatory and government bodies (both Indigenous and non-indigenous – and across local, regional and national scales) as well as by individuals. The survey results suggest that responsibility for adaptation is seen as lying more with individuals and not so much with communities or larger governmental structures. Adaptation measures are mainly physical, such as construction measures: e.g., shore protection against natural hazards such as increased coastal erosion. However, especially within Indigenous (government) approaches, the environment is seen as intricately intertwined with the human, socio-cultural and spiritual realm, suggesting a wider understanding of adaptation that takes more than just technical and physical processes into account. This is reflected in holistic approaches to adaptation focusing also, e.g., on language and cultural vitality and a two-way intergenerational knowledge transfer between Elders and Youth. Language & cultural vitality, Indigenous Knowledge and land skills (including flexibility, hazard avoidance and emergency preparedness) are seen both under threat by and as a resource for adapting to changing circumstances. At the same time adaptation is seen as an innate feature of Indigenous society, that sees itself as continuously adapting to ever changing circumstances in relation to the natural environment.

In some places, such as Tuktoyaktuk, adaptation practices are also justified in terms of ensuring the stable conditions necessary for oil & gas industry development and the hope for economic prosperity. At the same time, this view is critiqued by other segments of the population who emphasize that the large sums invested in costly adaptation measures could be employed in more socially equitable ways. In Aklavik, adaptation is regularly discussed in various co-management structures, for example at the local hunters and trappers committee meetings. While people generally are aware of changes that are happening there is a perceived need for a better scientific understanding of changes. While adaptation actions were in the past rather reactive, behavioral, technological and targeting everyday challenges, recent years have seen a shift towards more emphasis on long-term planning and targeted co-designed research – including the acknowledgement of mutual knowledge sharing and capacity building within and between scholarly and (policy) communities. In Aklavik, just as in Inuvik, Tuktoyaktuk and Fort McPherson, adaptation is seen as important and necessary. However, more adaptation actions are needed, and they should be supported and carried out in co-operation with decision-makers from different levels. This was also shown in the research carried out by the interdisciplinary research team who investigated relationships between variables of interest (wellbeing, quality of life, satisfaction with life, empowerment, health) and adaptation factors from the data of Canada by cross-tabulation. The descriptive results are based on the joint questionnaire survey collected in Aklavik and are also presented in the Deliverable 5.4. and in the supplements of the scientific paper written by a multidisciplinary research team (Timlin et al. 2022a). Overall, results suggested that not enough or somewhat enough has been done to adapt to or face the impacts of permafrost thaw on different levels, from individual to global actions. This was clearer between the variables of feeling of empowerment and self-rated health and adaptation actions from individual to local levels compared to the variables of life balance (sum variable of wellbeing, quality of life and satisfaction with life) where participants especially assessed that not enough was done on the regional to global level. Furthermore, assessment was clearer among participants who did not have a very strong life balance, high health level, or felt somewhat or not at all empowered to face the changes related to permafrost thaw. More specifically described results can be found from the scientific paper written by Timlin et al. (2022a).

6.2.4. Adaptive capacity

In global comparison, studies on adaptive capacity were conducted mostly in rich, industrialized countries (Siders 2018). Current literature suggests that Indigenous societies in Canada may be well-positioned in terms of environmental protection and successful adaptation (Vogel et al. 2022). Within the Inuvialuit Settlement (ISR) region 185 scientific studies focusing on permafrost and related issues were certified under the NWT research license between the years 1974 and 2023, with a large majority (132) approved between the years 2000 and now. Within the Gwich'in Settlement area (GSA) 109 projects were licensed between 1974 and 2023, also with a vast majority (97) again approved after the year 2000. Just within the last three years (2021 – 2023) 46 and 42 projects were licensed respectively in the ISR and GSA, pointing towards an exponential increase in projects over the period monitored. Scientific Studies within the ISR and GSA: Within

the Inuvialuit Settlement (ISR) region 185 scientific studies focusing on permafrost and related issues were certified under the NWT research license between the years 1974 and 2023, with a large majority (132) approved between the years 2000 and now. Within the Gwich'in Settlement area (GSA) 109 projects were licensed between 1974 and 2023, also with a vast majority (97) again approved after the year 2000. Just within the last three years (2021 – 2023) 46 and 42 projects were licensed respectively in the ISR and GSA, pointing towards an exponential increase in projects over the period monitored.

Figure 4: Government of Northwest Territories 2023 NWT research database (GNWT 2023).

Even if the search is narrowed down to projects that mention permafrost specifically in their project title, the numbers are still high: Fifty-seven scientific studies within the Inuvialuit Settlement (ISR) between 1974 and 2023, with forty-seven approved after 2000; and forty-three projects within the Gwich'in Settlement area between 2000 and 2023. Between 2021 – 2023, twenty-three and twenty-two projects licensed respectively in the ISR and GSA (GNWT 2023) This large number of studies conducted in the wider region points towards an increase not only in scientific interest and necessity but also a potential increase in adaptive capacity, with a consistently growing knowledge base. However, the question of effective knowledge transfer between the scientific community and local inhabitants remains.

6.3. Ilulissat, Disko Bay, West Greenland

With a population of nearly 5000 inhabitants Ilulissat is the third largest town in Greenland. Located on the coast of Disko Bay in western Greenland, Ilulissat is the administrative and main service center of Avannaata municipality, which was created in 2018 and encompasses more than

522 thousand square km, extending northward to the Nares Strait at 80 degrees north latitude. Avannaata includes four towns - Qaanaaq, Upernavik, Uummannaq and Ilulissat – and 23 villages or small settlements. The backbone of the Ilulissat economy consists of fisheries and tourism, but these sectors together with public services and construction provide most employment. The fisheries fleet includes both trawlers and smaller ships and boats, while halibut and shrimp are the main species that are processed in the local factories which rely to a significant extent on foreign employees. Benefiting from the proximity of the UNESCO World Heritage ice fjord, the settlement is particularly attractive for tourism development. Especially considering the ongoing construction of an international airport and an extended airstrip, a rapid increase in the number of residents, foreign employees, and tourists is expected. Therefore, there is a need for new and reliable facilities in the coming years for sustaining the development of Ilulissat. Housing and linear infrastructure are impacted by ground movements and permafrost degradation requiring significant repairs and maintenance operations, intensive site investigations and reconstruction work. Growth in economic activities and predicted rapid increase in the numbers of residents and visitors during the next several years pose elevated challenges; the expanded construction of infrastructure must be appropriately adapted to climate change impacts.

6.3.1. Methods

Using qualitative methods as well as a mixed-method questionnaire survey, fieldwork was carried out in Ilulissat by teams of researchers from the academic disciplines of social and health sciences, and civil engineering in the period 2019-2023. Community consultation meetings, interviews and group-discussions were conducted alternately in Danish, English, Kalaallisut and Icelandic. All interviewees signed informed-consent forms, and all sessions were recorded and transcribed and then written up in English, while research teams members also took notes which were subsequently assembled. Hired local interpreters took part in all sessions that included individuals who preferred the use of Kalaallisut, and researchers who spoke Danish translated the content to other researchers in English.

Our broad range of community consultation involved a variety of formal and informal settings and close engagements and dialogues with Ilulissat residents and experts as a way of obtaining as many accounts and perspectives as possible, including different types of knowledge and experience, as well as to foster an open, transparent, and inclusive co-production of knowledge. Fieldwork methods included a large pre-planned workshop; a town hall meeting; several prearranged focus groups; numerous smaller workshops in various workplaces, offices, businesses, and schools; numerous semi-structured interviews with one or several local, indigenous and expert individuals at a time; as well as participant observations and informal conversations – all of which contributed to enhancing our understanding and generating further questions and discussions.

In each of the settings time was set aside to explain our project, answer questions, and clarify key issues. The first formal consultation meeting was a preplanned invited workshop with city planners, government employees, technical experts, and private sector entrepreneurs that was organized and held in collaboration with city officials in 2019. In this initial workshop – and in the

town hall meeting and the numerous smaller workshops and focus groups that followed in 2019, 2021, 2022 and 2023 – the setting allowed for dynamic dialogue and open discussion where a variety of issues, challenges, opinions, and perspectives from different experts were brought to the table. For obtaining more detailed information and addressing technical questions, problems, and remedies, this was followed by scheduled interviews and follow-up meetings with selected individuals as well as others suggested by participants.

A final community workshop was held in Ilulissat in early 2023 and focused on risks, indicators, and adaptation strategies. This was an open workshop which included the participation of many experts and residents, many of whom had been interviewed earlier in various sessions and settings. The intensive workshop was followed by more than twenty in-depth interviews with city planners, government employees, technical experts, private sector entrepreneurs, and other local stakeholders to gather perspectives on adaptation and mitigation measures. In addition, a survey with questions on adaptation needs and strategies was distributed and 51 responses were collected.

6.3.2. Description of results and discussion

Extensive interviews with municipality representatives, technical personnel, private contractors, and business owners in Ilulissat over the period 2019-2022 revealed that perceived key risks from permafrost thaw are associated with all life domains but particularly with infrastructure and built environment, economy and material wellbeing, and fate control and planning. Adaptation and mitigation measures to address these risks were discussed in interview settings in the field seasons extending the full project period, but with a special emphasis in the final season in early 2023, as a final step in the project.

Foremost challenges associated with the impacts of permafrost thaw on infrastructure and the built environment constitute the frequent need for costly repairs and maintenance. As the ground sinks and cracks, buildings and linear infrastructure become destabilized and damaged. Interviewees would frequently comment on the deteriorating conditions of the roads, as wavy and full of holes, and many pointed out that the repeatedly implemented piecemeal repair of filling the holes after the snow and ice has melted are expensive but insufficient adaptive measures. Many alternative ad hoc and planned mitigative and adaptive measures were suggested such as using non-frost susceptible gravel or other material to create a layer of insulation. With respect to other linear infrastructure, interviews advocated placing pipes and wires above ground.

In general, interviewees called for the introduction of new and better technology coupled with closer monitoring of structures and permafrost conditions; however, some interviewees stated that the roads had been constructed differently and better in earlier times, e.g., “they used to remove the permafrost a couple of meters down, fill in with gravel, and place ventilation underneath the gravel”. One informant remarked, “we should build the roads the way they were built back in the times of GTO [Greenland’s Technical Organization (ca. 1950s-80s)]”, suggesting that a different and less costly technique for road construction is currently used. Interviewers sensed a tone of regret and frustration with the changes in technique, indicating that things have gotten worse. One construction representative commented: “The problem is that the budget for this type of road is

just not big enough, and even if they increased the budget ten-fold it would still not be enough, so it is not realistic to think that this will ever happen. But I know that in earlier days they placed isolation under the road and that seems to have had a positive effect, and the road stayed relatively flat”.

Interviewees also discussed new methods used to better safeguard housing and protect buildings from being damaged by thawing permafrost and other climate-related factors, including new techniques of installing windows with plastic rather than wooden frames. One interviewee explained: “Yes, plastic-frame windows, we are talking about this now, and the cost. They're cheap, at an affordable cost, and they are better than most of the wood-frame windows you can get. Because they maintain their form. So, they are a favorite product for us - they don't rot ”; and “In the last 5 years, we have changed more than 10,000 windows (to plastic type) across Greenland”. Also, housing representatives discussed a new method of re-leveling houses. One representative explained: “Re-levelling of houses (it’s a cheap way) and a new method here”, and “[in] Qaanaaq houses have wood foundations, and this makes it easier for us to fix the house. We lift the house; we lay some wood under it. We have done this with five houses in the last two years”.

The risks of permafrost thaw to economy and material wellbeing were emphasized by interviewees across sectors who made frequent reference to the higher costs due to permafrost thaw related impacts. Financial constraints and critical trade-offs were themes in many interviews which included such statements as: “We have no money to build. Much of our money goes into maintenance and repairs”, and “Sadly, it's all about money”. One interviewee, a technical expert, explained that things often end in small fixes because of lack of financial resources, especially after the municipal amalgamations (in 2009 and 2018) which resulted in Ilulissat now belonging to a much larger municipality than it did before. The expert continued by saying: “Our municipality gets a small bag of money, one at a time, not at all enough to do anything but small fixes, not enough to build a sustainable infrastructure”.

A housing representative also blamed the need to find cheap adaptation measures on lack of resources: “Our limit is the money. The building must be cheap. We address things when we find problems and solve them with the means we have, the money and the tools”. However, from a construction point of view, a contractor explained when reflecting on lessons learned, cheap solutions don’t work in permafrost areas: “If you are going to dig deeper, take a look at the machinery and don't choose the cheap solution”. Some interviewees also offered ideas about frameworks within which to implement more efficacious adaptation strategies in the future, including more public-private partnerships to share risks; the introduction of innovative risk models, e.g., models of shared financial risk between client and contractor which could also be part of the competition for a contract bid. These ideas emerged from discussions under the theme of needs for careful prioritization.

A common concern was also expressed by many interviewees from both private and public sectors about the risks to fate control and planning, which include risks related to a perceived lack of a common set of priorities between politicians, local planners, infrastructure experts and other holders of technical-environmental knowledge; lack of multiyear financial planning and strategy

for building, maintaining, and repairing of infrastructure; and risks related to the increased unknown(s), and a decreased sense of control. Overall, informants conveyed some lack of fate control and a strong sense of uncertainty associated with the need for long-term planning and appropriate measures in dealing with the impacts of permafrost thaw. Correspondingly, local adaptation measures are mostly ad hoc, such as much time spent planning, amending, and reassessing; keeping more (extra) materials in stock, since “delivery time of spare parts is our main concern”; using a few strongly built vehicles; and pressuring government and policy makers to act, e.g. “to try to address the situation of the road conditions we put pressure on the municipality to get them to dig down deeper rather than simply add more asphalt on top which does not solve the situation”. One transport company explained that what they need are the types of vehicles that are strongly built but not necessarily built for long-distance driving, i.e., vehicles with powerful springs and shock absorbers (dampers).

Risks associated with education and training, as perceived by interviewees, include the risks caused or compounded by lack of specialists to meet needs, a high turnover of employees, and knowledge being lost, all of which create challenges to effective adaptation and mitigation. For addressing these challenges local adaptation measures include more training to meet new demands and local-specific needs, information campaigns, better access to information, and learning from other permafrost regions via extensive sharing of knowledge and workable solutions across the Arctic. Several informants emphasized the need for educating experts and engineers and considered that collaboration with the engineering program in Sisimiut could provide a partial solution. Interviewees placed special emphasis on locally adapted training whereby drivers are trained with respect to special and often hazardous road conditions.

Concerning the frequently expressed need for more information and knowledge and the method of learning from other regions, one interviewee revealed that some local representatives have visited other Nordic regions and Canada to learn how others adapt to permafrost thaw. While also addressing the importance of knowledge and learning but focusing on dissemination and youth at the local level, a schoolteacher made the following statements: “My goal is to pass on knowledge to the young generation, and students, to make sure they are engaged and well-informed about climate change and its impacts. When adults don't listen, we need to reach the young generation. Social media and short films have been effective ways to engage the youth here”.

Challenges related to road conditions and associated wear and tear on vehicles were most specifically addressed by representatives of the transport sector, who described how the industry seeks to adapt by training their own mechanics to avoid having to send equipment out for repair, and thereby saving time and resources. Delivery time of spare parts is a critical concern in these remote regions. The most important strategies are the appropriate training and education of drivers and the purchase of the right equipment, e.g., and most desirably, a type of vehicles used abroad that are easier to maintain and that have elaborate suspension systems including powerful springs and shock absorbers and are thus better suited for our use. The transport industry considers the types of vehicles that are strongly built but not necessarily built for long-distance driving. One interviewee explained: “It is important that our drivers adapt to the special conditions; it is not

about getting to your destination 10 km faster per hour; that would only increase the vehicle damage and wear and tear here. So, it's about training and educating our drivers to take special care and drive carefully according to the conditions and avoid bumps"; and "there are places in town where you need to be patient and wait for oncoming traffic to pass to avoid a bump. So, to exercise patience is also a part of the training". To address the situation of the road conditions, the industry also puts pressure on the municipality "to get them to dig down deeper rather than simply add more asphalt on top which does not solve the situation".

The adaptive measures that interviewees mentioned as important means to counter and guard against the adverse impacts of permafrost thaw on health and wellbeing concern the risks of road hazards and vehicle accidents, on the one hand, and risks associated with poor water quality, supply, sanitation, and hygiene. Several informants proclaimed that they drive extra cautiously when they might expect to run into big potholes in the road or when they are near steep slopes where rock- or mudslides may occur, particularly in construction areas. Having special road safety officers on staff, both for training drivers and for being on the watch where road hazards are most likely to happen, are adaptive strategies that should be collectively implemented. Concerning the need for a supply of water that promotes health and wellbeing, informants described adaptive and precautionary measures whereby adults sail out to sea and procure large pieces of ice which they bring back to town where this water was used in homes instead of the tap water that was considered contaminated or polluted.

Continuing the discussion of strategies for confronting the risks posed by unsafe water while addressing the theme of water and food security, interviewees emphasized an array of adaptive means which are implemented regularly, on occasion or should be carried out more effectively and comprehensively due to ongoing impacts of permafrost thaw and other environmental changes as well as industrial activities. These adaptation measures include, first, the boiling of water for home use. Second, the moving of water pipes, construction of new aqueducts and building of new water purifying systems, but currently these are in Ilulissat where the road to the new airport is being built. Third, moving (constructing) a water reservoir to (at) a new and safer location. One salient reason for moving the reservoir used as a source of water supply for Ilulissat residents is the fact that there is salt water beneath the permafrost layer under this artificial lake and hence the risk of salt contamination of the town's main source of fresh water. Fourth, but not least, the regular monitoring of water quality is a crucial means toward maintaining water security. Furthermore, for these regular measures to be utmost effective and useful as an adaptation strategy it is important that the tests and analysis of the water quality can be conducted locally. Hence several interviewees on this subject concurred that regular monitoring of the quality of fresh water in Disko Bay was rendered less effectual when a laboratory in Ilulissat closed and thus water samples are currently being sent to Nuuk for analysis.

Additional data on existing adaptation strategies for Greenland were obtained during a project workshop (general assembly) of Nunataryuk scientists who conduct fieldwork in Greenland. This included adjustment of foundations in the case of Qaanaaq, the re-pavement of roads and

improvement of sewer systems in the case of Ilulissat and Sisimiut, and the implementation of new building codes to regulate foundation work in permafrost areas.

The case of Ilulissat has shown - based on extensive interview material collected over a period of three years - that permafrost thaw poses risks to several life domains that are important to overall human wellbeing. At the same time, interview data has also suggested that persistent and growing risks from permafrost thaw are the result of limited financial resources, and that solutions to overcome permafrost related risks include solving existing budgetary challenges. While a variety of adaptation measures are in use (e.g. road maintenance and repair; cooling system under slumping floor; training of personnel) representatives from private and public sectors point to a lack of financial resources to implement sufficient measures for effective adaptation. Lack of financial resources may necessitate prioritization which in turn can lead to critical trade-offs and amplify the negative impacts from thawing permafrost (see also Larsen et al. 2022 (Nunataryuk Deliverable Report 9.4)).

6.4. Republic of Sakha (Yakutiya), North-East Siberia, Russia

Our greater case study region includes Bulunskiy Ulus (District) of the Republic of Sakha (Yakutiya) in North-East Siberia, Russia. Tiksi, the administrative center of Bulunskiy District, was founded in 1932 as a port city along the Northern Sea Route (NSR) during the heyday of Soviet exploration, urbanization and industrialization of the Arctic. Located at the delta of the Lena River, it became a vibrant urban settlement, an important transshipment node and later also a headquarters to a military base. In the year of 1989, which marked the community's development peak, its local population exceeded 11,000 and the sea port was bustling with cargo ships delivering an assortment of goods and foods to local residents (Gukov 2013; Struchkov 2005). In the post-Soviet years, Tiksi as most of other communities in the Russian Arctic, has been experiencing population decline, reconfiguration of transportation system and socio-economic and environmental changes. Yet, the town is still proudly called "the Arctic sea-gate of Yakutiya" and is a maritime and riverine transportation node. The current national program of the NSR modernization is filled with the promises and plans of the reconstruction of the sea port and community development, which have been remaining only on paper. The present permanent (civilian) population counts up to ca 4600 residents, with roughly one third of Sakha (Yakut) people, one third of indigenous numerically small groups (primarily, Evenki and Eveny people), and one third of Russian settlers. Most of them are employed in the local fishing economy, small-scale trade, and public services (Schweitzer and Povoroznyuk 2022).

The rural community of Bykovskiy is located on the Bykovskiy Peninsula, 40 km away by sea from Tiksi. It is the largest indigenous (primarily Evenki) fishing community in the Bulunskiy District founded in 1940 during the Soviet collectivization and sedentization of nomadic population. Forced relocations and deportation of political prisoners from the Baltic states to the area in the 1940-1950s added to the ethnic diversity but also to the dark past of the community. Post-Soviet socio-economic transformations resulted in the reorganization of the fishing economy and competition for marine resources with non-local stakeholders. However, the local fishing

enterprise “Kolkhoz “Arktika”” still keeps most of the population occupied, while also providing basic social security and access to subsistence resources (fish and others) to slightly over 500 local residents (Gorokhov 2002; Stammler et al. 2017). The community faces severe and progressing coastal erosion caused by permafrost thaw and other natural forces and changes (Lantuit et al. 2011).

6.4.1. Methods

The data for this case study region were collected during anthropological fieldwork in the capital city of Yakutsk and the communities of Tiksi and Bykovskiy in the Republic of Sakha (Yakutiya) in July 2019. Our fieldwork methods included observations, community meetings, focus groups and in-depth interviews with local and indigenous residents, expert interviews with representatives of administrations and NGOs, as well as work with local archives. The fieldwork started with a series of meetings in research institutes and public organizations in Yakutsk and continued with an introductory community meeting accompanied by a round table discussion in the local administration in Tiksi. In the process of fieldwork, 3 focus groups and 22 interviews with the residents and experts, as well as the current local reports on and plans of socio-economic development were gathered. While we initially intended to return to the region in order to conduct follow-up fieldwork and a community workshop on local risks, indicators and adaptation to permafrost thaw, the COVID-19 pandemics and later Russia’s war in Ukraine made these plans for further research impossible.

6.4.2. Description of results

The analysis of our field data has shown that residents of the studied communities in northern Sakha (Yakutiya) have been adapting or responding to various impacts of thawing permafrost in multiple ways. In the infrastructural domain, they stopped the construction of new buildings and moved or abandoned the old ones lying in the zone of coastal erosion in Bykovskiy. In response to the malfunctioning of ice roads, the season of delivery of goods and food to local communities was shortened. Likewise, decreased functionality of ice cellars in summers, has led to shortening of the period of storage of fish and other food. Destabilization of urban infrastructure and disruption of on-ground transportation is partially mitigated by ad hoc repairs and partially by monitoring and assessment initiatives that do not always solve the issues.

In response to (potential) health-related impacts presumably connected to permafrost thaw, such as industrial pollution of water and marine resources, observation of the visible signs of pollution and refusal from consumption of water and fish from polluted rivers and coastal areas are practiced. Local activists also call public attention to the problem of potential soil and water contamination with dormant viral infections (e.g. anthrax) associated with the coastal erosion and opening of graves in the process of destruction of the cemetery of political prisoners relocated to the region during Stalinist repressions, in Bykovskiy. At the same time, impacts of permafrost thaw on the food delivery and storage of subsistence products leads to an unhealthy shift to and dependence

on low quality food with longer periods of storage available in local stores. This trend can be seen as an example of a negative adaptation strategy.

Thawing permafrost also entails a number of economic losses, especially those caused by malfunctioning ice roads and destruction of urban infrastructure. Due to the lack of funds needed to mitigate their consequences, other means of adaptation such as a shortened season of supply and relocation of destabilized houses are chosen.

Indigenous and local residents involved in subsistence activities (fishing and reindeer herding) are affected and often endangered by transformation of the landscape (growing swampiness of the tundra) and changing salinity of the water along the coast (no fish near the coast). To reduce the risks connected with driving out to the tundra with a snowmobile, they reduce travel in the seasons and icing and melting. Likewise, they don't sail out far into the sea in stormy weather. All these changes, in combination with other factors, reduce quality of life and productivity of traditional economic practices and push permanent residents, especially younger people, out of the communities to look for better opportunities elsewhere.

Transformation of natural landscapes results in reduction of opportunities for subsistence and traditional ways of life, especially for indigenous groups. While in some cases it leads to the loss of culture and language, in others, it results in a greater reliance on traditional knowledge and practices of adaptation to the changing environment is articulated and demonstrated. Yet in others, climate skepticism or optimism are voiced as reactions to overwhelming but often threatening and misleading information about climate change transmitted by local, regional and national media. Such skepticism and distrust is often combined with the seeming ignorance or disregard even to the most obvious impacts of permafrost thaw. We argue that these attitudes can be, in fact, also interpreted as forms of psychological, emotional and cognitive adaptation to environmental change processes in the context of disempowerment.

In the cultural domain, unsuccessful attempts to fortify the coastline as a measure of adaptation to coastal erosion leading to destruction of a sacred and cultural heritage site (the cemetery), made by the local administration, failed because of the lack of resources¹. On the other hand, the growing informal industry of excavation of mammoth tusk appearing because of thawing ground, destructs landscapes, including archeological and cultural sites. Regulation measures proposed by some experts in response to this practice, still need to be implemented.

The adaptation practices in the domain of planning and fate control most often include expert assessments of endangered infrastructure objects and areas, monitoring of roads and other transport infrastructure, recommendations on adoption of norms and regulations on mapping, protection and use of permafrost-rich areas. These measures are often undertaken by the expert community of

¹ In Russia, resources for the fortification of the coastline should be allocated from the regional and federal budgets. The local municipalities usually have very limited budgets filled only due to revenues from income tax. Such unbalanced distribution of financial and other resources between different levels of power leads to growing centralization and authoritarianism where local communities are found in the most unfavorable position.

permafrost scientists based primarily in the city of Yakutsk but closely familiar with the permafrost conditions in the Republic of Sakha (Yakutiya). One of the most successful examples in this regard is the rather unique „Law on Protection of Permafrost Thaw“ recently adopted by the Parliament of the Republic of Sakha (Yakutiya)². Still, experts complain that most of their recommendations for adaptation and mitigation of the impacts of permafrost degradation lack implementation or even a mere understanding. Another connected adaptation measure falling into the domain of education and proposed by experts is dissemination of knowledge about permafrost both among the public and the politicians while focusing on training and preparing decision-makers for the adoption of regulations needed to protect and prevent further degradation of permafrost in the republic.

6.4.3. Discussion and conclusions

Indigenous and local residents of the region have a long history of observing and adapting to environmental changes (Graybill 2013; Ksenofontov et al. 2017). At the same time, the unprecedented speed of these changes and unpredictability of the impacts of thawing permafrost on stability and functioning of infrastructures, mobility, subsistence and supply, health, water and food security, and cultural vitality, challenge the adaptation process. There are also a number of other epistemological, economic, political, legal and administrative challenges to adaptation of local residents of the region to permafrost thaw. The disjuncture between different types of knowledge – local/indigenous/traditional, on the one hand, and expert knowledge, on the other, coupled with the lack of public attention and even recognition of climate change impacts, lead to the lack of reliable and publicly accessible information about the environmental change processes. Furthermore, the lack of financial resources for implementation of adaptation measures on the local level, where the most of the impacts are happening, makes Arctic communities in North-East Siberia vulnerable subjects rather than agents able to easily adapt to permafrost degradation. Highly centralized political power when the responsibility for citizens’ wellbeing is delegated to the local level while most of the resources remain concentrated on the federal level, leads to disempowerment of communities and individuals and kills grassroot adaptation initiatives. Not surprisingly, most Arctic residents in two studies of local communities feel powerless or incapable of coping with the larger environmental and political forces and processes.

In this context, passive or negative forms of adaptation prevail over (pro)active adaptation to climate change and permafrost thaw. The existing regional scientific community has accumulated a strong expertise in the area of permafrost thaw, on the basis of which multiple expert assessments, reports and recommendations are regularly produced. Those address mostly engineering and construction bureaus and companies, as well as decision-makers, researchers of across the disciplines and activists. However, in practice, their recommendations remain on paper due to the lack of political will or funds, or, most often, because of the combination of both. In this situation local residents are not able to actively adapt to the impacts of permafrost thaw on the physical and

² The Law of the Republic of Sakha (Yakutiya) On Efficient Use and Protection of Permafrost.

material levels, and, thus, are not able to keep control over their future. And so, other less tangible – psychological, cognitive and emotional forms of adaptation, are manifested. Therefore, (apparent) ignorance, skepticism or optimism in relation to most obvious environmental change impacts should not be taken for granted as they, but rather should be interpreted as (protective) reactions against uncontrollable, unpredictable and often threatening natural, social and political processes (Povoroznyuk and Schweitzer 2023).

7. Discussion and concluding comments

Thawing permafrost creates risks to the environment, economy and culture in Arctic coastal communities. Overall, the conceptual risk framework (Larsen et al. 2021) developed earlier in the Nunataryuk project period with its Compass model and methodological flow chart, in which we incorporate the dual dimensions of risk, has proven to be an effective framework for studying thawing permafrost in Arctic coastal communities and for devising indicators and as a framework for discussing tools and strategies for adaptation and mitigation.

A risk framework was developed as a first step in the co-production process between Nunataryuk researchers and locals to help devise steps forward to identify impacts, risks, and adaptation strategies (Larsen et al. 2021; Larsen et al. 2022). In co-production with locals and guided by the risk framework and its Compass model and methodological flowchart (see section 4.0 above), Nunataryuk researchers early on in the process identified the main life domains associated with permafrost thaw impacts in the four case study regions along the Arctic Coast; Ilulissat and Qeqertarsuaq, West Greenland; Longyearbyen, Svalbard; Beaufort Sea Area and Mackenzie River Delta, Canada; and Northern Sakha (Yakutiya), Russia, as well as the perceived risks from permafrost thaw within each of these life domains. This was followed by a process to devise a set of Arctic social and biophysical indicators for measuring and monitoring the impact of permafrost thaw and the effectiveness of adaptation strategies. In this current step adaptation measures have been identified, analysed and sorted according to the key life domain areas in co-production with local stakeholders.

In addition, an important step in the project process has been to conduct three community workshops co-funded by the University of the Arctic; the first one was held in Ilulissat, Greenland; the second in Inuvik and Aklavik, Canada; and the third and final one in Longyearbyen, Svalbard. The purpose of these workshops was to discuss, share, and validate the research results on key impacts and risks from permafrost thaw with local communities. This served as a platform for feedback and discussion with Indigenous and local people, policymakers and other stakeholders, including other scientists. In combination with findings from qualitative research in all study sites, this contributed important input for the designing of Arctic social and biophysical indicators, and the exploration of adaptation and mitigation strategies in co-production with local residents and stakeholders in each of our case study regions. The work on developing Arctic social and biophysical indicators and identifying and illustrating adaptation and mitigation strategies will contribute to reducing the identified key risks from permafrost thaw.

As a first step, ahead of identifying adaptation strategies, the data on impacts and risks from permafrost thaw were gathered and analyzed. On the impacts of permafrost thaw, the overarching themes in all study sites include a focus on the built environment, and heritage sites. Further, interview results have shown that subsistence, linked to health, food security and cultural vitality is of paramount importance in all study sites except Longyearbyen, which does not have an Indigenous population. Interview results show that perceived key risks from permafrost thaw in Ilulissat are associated with all life domains but particularly with infrastructure and built environment, economy and material wellbeing, and fate control and planning, whereas risks to other life domains - health and wellbeing, water and food security, and cultural wellbeing - are less likely to be attributed specifically or solely to permafrost thaw. In the case of the Beaufort Sea Region, Yukon Coast and Mackenzie River Delta, Canada, increased permafrost thaw is largely considered having a negative impact on life, with infrastructure failure being a main concern. In Longyearbyen, Svalbard, people generally associate permafrost thaw with negative changes, primarily associated with destabilization of buildings and landslides and avalanches. However, many participants emphasized that permafrost thaw does not cause problems to them personally, a finding that was confirmed in the survey conducted.

As a further step, interviews and workshops were conducted in all study sites to gather data on strategies to adapt to these key risks identified earlier in the process. Results suggest that both ad hoc adaptation and planned adaptation are carried out within all the quality-of-life domains included in this study.

In addition, survey results (Longyearbyen, Aklavik, Ilulissat) show important similarities and differences across case study regions in local perceptions regarding adaptation. Housing, infrastructure, and traditional knowledge are perceived by locals as the most important areas to adapt to facilitate day-to-day activities. Respondents in Longyearbyen perceive that “housing” is the area where the community is best prepared to adapt, whereas in the case of Aklavik and Ilulissat - which are predominantly indigenous communities - respondents perceive “traditional knowledge” as the area where the community is best prepared.

Survey results further show that differences exist in whether and where respondents feel enough is being done to adapt or face the impacts related to permafrost thaw: while the majority of respondents across field sites generally agree or somewhat agree that enough is being done at the global level and by local and national authorities (with the exception of Longyearbyen), differences exist with respect to the community level and individuals, with the majority of respondents in Aklavik and Ilulissat answer that enough is being done at that level.

Moreover, interview results from a variety of interview settings show that while a range of adaptation measures are in use (e.g. road maintenance and repair; cooling system under slumping floor; training of personnel; definition of risk zones; relocation; monitoring of water quality, etc.) representatives from the private and public sectors often point to a lack of financial resources to implement sufficient measures for effective adaptation. Furthermore, climate change was highlighted as a factor increasing uncertainties and thus challenging adaptation. Results from interviews with locals from each of the case study regions suggest that constraints to adaptation

include several of the list of factors summarized by the IPCC (IPCC 2014), (e.g. limited integration or coordination of governance, uncertainties about projected impacts; different perceptions of risks; competing values; limited tools to monitor adaptation effectiveness).

Effective adaptation in the case study sites is compromised by the following factors that act as constraints to implementation: Limited financial and human resources, which is noted as a concern across the case study sites; limited integration or coordination of governance – a point often emphasized; uncertainties about projected impacts, which was discussed at the local level in terms of the need for more knowledge and information campaigns; different perceptions of risks, which was reflected in the extensive interviews with different stakeholders; competing values – as seen between different goals of economic sectors, public and private and the traditional sector, as well as reflected in many of the extensive interviews; absence of key adaptation leaders and advocates – which in some of the case study sites was expressed as a lack of central and municipality leadership in the area of climate change impacts and adaptation; limited tools to monitor adaptation effectiveness – which was demonstrated in extensive interviews and discussions on the identification and development of Arctic and bio-physical indicators to monitor impacts and for measuring the effectiveness of adaptation strategies (for a discussion of factors that compromise adaptation see IPCC 2014). Furthermore, in Longyearbyen and Ilulissat interview partners emphasized that the technical solutions to adapt to permafrost thaw exist, and that the challenges are rather economic and political, but also in some cases social, as turnover of staff has turned out to constitute a major challenge for successful adaptation. In Russia, adaptation measure suggested by the expert community are not implemented because of a lack of political will, financial resources and a gap between expert and local knowledge about environmental change, as well as miscommunication between responsible local, regional, and federal authorities on the one hand, and the public, on the other.

More effective adaptation must include better access to human, technical, and financial resources; participatory processes which enhance community engagement and co-production of knowledge, including the integration of local, traditional and informal knowledge; and an effective monitoring system that include co-produced Arctic social and bio-physical indicators. As also pointed to earlier, a major challenge identified across the case study sites is the lack of financial and human and technical resources which are needed for successful and a more just and equitable adaptation process to take place, and to ensure an outcome that does not leave a community more vulnerable.

Due to these challenges of major resource constraints, and as we heard in dialogue with different groups of local stakeholders, important trade-offs between divergent views and priorities may be needed, which in turn can challenge the outcome or process of adaptation and prospects for future resilience and local sustainability. Another ethical dilemma is that while effective adaptation may be possible, it may not be the most desired on all ethical grounds, e.g. such as in a case of relocation due to permafrost thaw, or when pipelines or other infrastructure are moved to areas where they may coincide or interfere with wildlife pasture or migration.

Overall, with adaptation planning and implementation being contingent on societal values and risk perceptions (which are highly diverse) the process is fundamentally one that can lead to inequities

and critical economic and social trade-offs. Inequalities can be exacerbated if consideration of ethical and just outcomes are not included in discussions and decision-making, which in turn can have consequences for overall human wellbeing in the affected communities. People and societies may perceive or rank risks and potential benefits differently, given diverse values and goals, and different societal contexts. As competing values, differences of interests, and potentially critical trade-offs between interests of different stakeholders exist, such factors need to be identified and considered in future research.

Differences in social and economic contexts and other non-climatic factors lead to differences in vulnerability and exposure across local sites. When inequities exist - social, economic, cultural, political, institutional - this may affect not only the nature and extent of vulnerabilities to permafrost thaw but also how adaptation and mitigation responses, planning, and implementation play out. A more just and equitable outcome in terms of adaptation and mitigation responses requires that risk management and adaptation strategies reflect the diversity of culture and society. Inclusion of ethical considerations requires an understanding of local complexities and the many stressors affecting local wellbeing, and therefore a well-coordinated process of co-production. For ethical reasons the divergence of views must be heard and incorporated into strategies, process design, planning and implementation which requires broad participation, inclusiveness and listening to unrecognized or silenced stakeholders, including the traditional or non-market sector.

Finally, the methodological flow chart and processual model developed as part of a risk management framework has proven effective as a tool for co-production of knowledge, for organizing and conducting workshops, focus groups and interviews to collect, discuss, and reflect on effective adaptation and mitigation strategies. But ultimately, adaptation and mitigation strategies (as well as indicators) presented in this research will need to be tested, validated, and adjusted in future settings between researchers and local stakeholders.

8. References

- Adger, W. N., Barnett, J., Brown, K., Marshall, N. and O'Brien, K. 2013. *Nature Climate Change*, 3, 112-117.
- Amundsen, H., Berglund, F. and Westskog, H. 2010. Overcoming barriers to climate change adaptation: a question of multilevel governance? *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy*, 28, 276-289.
- Asong, Z. E., Elshamy, M. E., Princz, D., Wheeler, H. S., Pomeroy, J. W., Pietroniro, A., & Cannon, A. 2020. High-resolution meteorological forcing data for hydrological modelling and climate change impact analysis in the Mackenzie River Basin. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 12, 629-645.
- Barnes, J., Dove, M., Lahsen, M., Mathews, A., McElwee, P., McIntosh, R., Moore, F., O'Reilly, J., Orlove, B., Puri, R., Weiss, H., & Yager, K. 2013. Contribution of anthropology to the study of climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 3(6), 541-544.
- Box, J. E., Colgan, W. T., Christensen, T. R., Schmidt, N. M., Lund, M., Parmentier, F.-J. W., Brown, R., Bhatt, U. S., Euskirchen, E. S., Romanovsky, V. E., Walsh, J. E., Overland, J. E., Wang, M., Corell, R. W., Meier, W. N., Wouters, B., Mernild, S., Mård, J., Pawlak, J. and Olsen, M. S. 2019. Key indicators of Arctic climate change: 1971-2017. *Environmental Research Letters*, 14(4), 45010.
- Bush, E. and Lemmen, D.S. (Eds). 2019. *Canada's changing climate report*. Government of Canada, Ottawa, ON.
- Christiansen, H. H., Gilbert, G. L., Demidov, N., Guglielmin, M., Isaksen, K., Marzena, O. and Boike, J. 2019. *Permafrost temperatures and active layer thickness in Svalbard during 2017/2018 (PermaSval)*. SESS Report 2019.
- Crate, S. 2008. Gone the Bull of Winter? Grappling with the Cultural Implications of and Anthropology's Role(s) in Global Climate Change. *Current Anthropology*, 49(4), 569-595.
- Few, R., Spear, D., Singh, C., Tebboth, M. G. L., Davies, J. E. and Thompson-Hall, M. C. 2020. Culture as a mediator of climate change adaptation: Neither static nor unidirectional. *WIREs Climate Change*, 12(1).
- Fiske, S.J., Crate, S.A., Crumley, C.L., Galvin, K., Lazrus, H., Lucero, L. Oliver-Smith, A., Orlove, B., Strauss, S., Wilk, R. 2014. *Changing the Atmosphere: Anthropology and Climate Change. Final report of the AAA Global Climate Change Task Force*. Arlington, VA: American Anthropological Association.
- Ford, J.D., Couture, N., Bell, T., Clark, D.G. 2018. Climate change and Canada's north coast: Research trends, progress, and future directions. *NRC Res. Press*, 26, 82-92.

- Ford, J. and Furgal, C. 2009. Foreword to the special issue: climate change impacts, adaptation and vulnerability in the Arctic. *Polar Research*, 28(1), 1-9.
- Ford, J. and Smit, B. 2004. A Framework for Assessing the Vulnerability of Communities in the Canadian Arctic to Risks Associated with Climate Change. *Arctic*, 57(4), 389-400.
- Ford, J., McDowell, G. and Pearce, T. 2015. The adaptation challenge in the Arctic. *Nature Clim. Change*, 5(12), 1046-1053.
- Ghorbani A., Siddiki, S. & Bravo, G. 2023. Editorial: Institutional adaptation and transformation for climate resilience. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 11:1159923.
- GNWT. 2023. Government of Northwest Territories research database. Available online: <https://data.researchlicensing.ece.gov.nt.ca/>
- Gorokhov, S.N. 2002. 'Arktika': A Fishing Cooperative on the Shores of the Arctic Ocean. Yakutsk: Bichik.
- Gukov, A. 2013. *The City of Tiksi*. Moscow: Printkom (in Russian)
- Graybill, J. K. 2013. Imagining Resilience: Situating Perceptions and Emotions about Climate Change on Kamchatka, Russia. *GeoJournal*, 78(5):817-832.
- Hanssen-Bauer, I., E.J. Førland, H. Hisdal, S. Mayer, A.B. Sandsø and A. Sorteberg. 2019. *Climate in Svalbard 2100 - A knowledge base for climate adaptation*. Oslo: Norwegian Environmental Agency.
- Head, L. 2010. Cultural ecology: adaptation - retrofitting a concept? *Progress in Human Geography*, 34(2), 234-242.
- Hovelsrud, G. K. and Smit, B. (Eds.). 2010. *Community Adaptation and Vulnerability in Arctic Regions*. Dordrecht, Heidelberg, London, New York: Springer.
- Hovelsrud, G. K., Poppel, B., van Oort, B. and Reist, J. D. 2011. Arctic Societies, Cultures, and Peoples in a Changing Cryosphere. *AMBIO*, 40, 100-110.
- Hovelsrud, G. K., White, J. L., Andrachuk, M., Smith, B. 2010. Community Adaptation and Vulnerability Integrated. In B. Smith and G. K. Hovelsrud (Eds.) *Community Adaptation and Vulnerability in Arctic Regions*. Dordrecht, Heidelberg, London, New York: Springer. pp. 335-348.
- Hulme, M. 2009. *Why We Disagree about Climate Change: Understanding Controversy, Inaction and Opportunity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- IPCC. 2014. *Summary for policymakers. Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part A: Global and Sectoral Aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Field, C.B., V.R. Barros, D.J. Dokken, K.J. Mach, M.D. Mastrandrea, T.E. Bilir, M. Chatterjee,

K.L. Ebi, Y.O. Estrada, R.C. Genova, B. Girma, E.S. Kissel, A.N. Levy, S. MacCracken, P.R. Mastrandrea, and L.L. White (eds.]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA

- IRC - Inuvialuit Regional Corporation. 2016. *Inuvialuit on the frontline of climate change: Development of a regional climate change adaptation strategy*. Available online: <https://irc.inuvialuit.com/system/files/Inuvialuit%20on%20the%20Frontline%20of%20Climate%20Change-Final-Feb2018%20%28SMALL%29.pdf> (accessed on November 16, 2022)
- Irrgang, A.M., Lantuit, H., Gordon, R.R., Piskor, A. and Manson, G.K. 2019. Impacts of past and future coastal changes on the Yukon coast—threats for cultural sites, infrastructure, and travel routes. *Arct. Sci.*, 5, 107–126.
- Keskitalo, E. C. H., Dannevig, H., Hovelsrud, G. K., West, J. J. and Swartling, Å. G. 2011. Adaptive capacity determinants in developed states: examples from the Nordic countries and Russia. *Reg Environ Change* 11:579–592.
- Keskitalo, E. C. and Kulyasova, A. 2009. The role of governance in community adaptation to climate change. *Polar Research* 28.
- Krupnik, I. 1993. *Arctic Adaptations: Native Whalers and Reindeer Herders of Northern Eurasia*. Hanover: University Press of New England.
- Ksenofontov, S., N. Backhaus and G. Schaeppman-Strub. 2017. ‘To Fish or not to Fish?’: Fishing Communities of Arctic Yakutia in the Face of Environmental Change and Political Transformations. *Polar Record* 53(3):289-303
- Lantuit, H., D. Atkinson, P.P. Overduin, M. Grigoriev, V. Rachold, G. Grosse and Hubberten, H.-W. 2011. Coastal Erosion Dynamics on the Permafrost-dominated Bykovsky Peninsula, North Siberia, 1951–2006. *Polar Research*, 30(1).
- Lantz, T. C. And Kokelj, S. V. 2008. Increasing rates of retrogressive thaw slump activity in the Mackenzie Delta region, N.W.T., Canada. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 35(6), L06502–n/a.
- Lantz, T.C. and Turner, K.W. 2015. Changes in lake area in response to thermokarst processes and climate in Old Crow Flats, Yukon. *J. Geophys. Res. Biogeosci.*, 120, 513–524.
- Larsen, J. N., Gartler, S., Meyer, A., Ingimundarson, J. H., Povoroznyuk, O. and Schweitzer, P. 2022. *Risk model, with identified key risks*. Nunataryuk Deliverable Report 9.4.
- Larsen, J. N., Schweitzer, P., Abass, K., Doloisio, N., Gartler, S., Ingeman-Nielsen, T., Ingimundarson, J. H., Jungsberg, L., Meyer, A., Rautio, A., Scheer, J., Timlin, U., Vanderlinden, J.-P. and Vullierme, M. 2021. Thawing Permafrost in Arctic Coastal Communities: A Framework for Studying Risks from Climate Change. *Sustainability*, 13(5), 2651.

- Marino, E. 2015. *Fierce Climate, Sacred Ground: An Ethnography of Climate Change in Shishmaref*. Fairbanks: University of Alaska Press.
- Meyer, A. and Sokolíčková, Z. Forthcoming. 'Melting Worlds' and 'Climate Myths': Diverging Stories of Climate Change in Longyearbyen, an Arctic 'Frontline Community'. Accepted.
- Meyer, A. 2022. Physical and feasible: Climate change adaptation in Longyearbyen, Svalbard. *Polar Record* 58: e29.
- Naess, L. O. 2013. The role of local knowledge in adaptation to climate change. *Wiley interdisciplinary reviews: Climate Change* 4(2).
- Nakashima, D., Galloway McLean, K., Thulstrup, H., Ramos Castillo, A. and Rubis, J. 2012. *Weathering Uncertainty: Traditional Knowledge for Climate Change Assessment and Adaptation*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Nelson, D. R., West, C. T. and Finan, T. J. 2009. Introduction to "In Focus: Global Change and Adaptation in Local Places". *American Anthropologist* 111(3), 271-274.
- Norsk Klimaservicesenter. 2019. *Klimaprofil Longyearbyen. Et kunnskapsgrunnlag for klimatilpasning*, Oslo: Norsk Klimaservicesenter.
- O'Brien, K. and Wolf, J. 2010. A values-based approach to vulnerability and adaptation to climate change. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change* 1(2), 232-242.
- O'Brien, K., Eriksen, S., Nygaard, L. P. and Schjolden, A. 2007. Why different interpretations of vulnerability matter in climate change discourses. *Climate Policy* 7(1), 73-88.
- O'Brien, K., Sygna, L. and Haugen, J. 2004. Vulnerable or Resilient? A Multi-Scale Assessment of Climate Impacts and Vulnerability in Norway. *Climatic Change* 64(1), 193-225.
- Oliver-Smith, A. 2017. Adaptation, vulnerability, and resilience: contested concepts in the anthropology of climate change. In H. Kopnina and E. Shoreman-Ouimet (Eds.) *Routledge Handbook of Environmental Anthropology*. London and New York: Routledge. Pp. 206-218.
- Pedersen, T. 2017. The politics of presence: the Longyearbyen dilemma. *Arctic Review on Law and Politics*, 8, 95–108.
- Povoroznyuk, O. and P. Schweitzer. 2023. Ignoring environmental change? On fishing quotas and collapsing coastlines in Bykovskiy, Northern Sakha (Yakutiya). *Ambio*.
- Ramage, J., Jungsberg, L., Meyer, A., and Gartler, S. 2022. 'No longer solid': perceived impacts of permafrost thaw in three Arctic communities. *Polar Geography* 45(3), 226-239.
- Ramage, J., Jungsberg, L., Wang, S., Gartler, S., Meyer, A., Timlin, U., Rautio, A., Abass, K. and Heleniak, T. 2020. *Identifying and recognizing the value of provisioning permafrost ecosystem services in the Arctic*. Nunataryuk Deliverable Report 7.5.

- Ramage, J., Irrgang, A., Morgenstern, A., Herzsuh, U. and Lantuit, H. 2016. Distribution and Evolution of Coastal Retrogressive Thaw Slumps along the Yukon Coast, Canada. In *Proceedings of the International Conference On Permafrost*, Potsdam, Germany, 20–24 June 2016.
- Räsänen, A., Juhola, S. and Nygren, A. 2016. Climate change, multiple stressors and human vulnerability: a systematic review. *Regional Environmental Change* 16(8), 22291-22302.
- Ribot, J. 2014. Cause and response: vulnerability and climate in the Anthropocene. *Journal of Peasant Studies*, 41(5), 667-705.
- Schweitzer, P. and Povoroznyuk, O. 2022. Infrastructural legacies and post-Soviet transformations in Northern Sakha (Yakutiya), Russia. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 4, 297-308.
- Siders, A. R. 2019. Adaptive capacity to climate change: A synthesis of concepts, methods, and findings in a fragmented field. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews. Climate Change*, 10(3), e573–n/a.
- Smit, B. and Pilifosova, O. 2001. Adaptation to climate change in the context of sustainable development and equity. In J. J. McCarthy, O. F. Canziani, N. A. Leary, D. J. Dokken and White, K. S. (Eds.). *Climate change 2001: impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press. Pp. 877-912.
- Sinitsyn, A., Westermann, S., Arlov, T., Landgren, O., Meyer, A. Lutz, J. and Bekele, Y., 2022. *PCCH-Arctic -Polar Climate and Cultural Heritage -Preservation and Restoration Management*. Project presentation and current results. Conference Presentation at Frostdagen 2022 at Norwegian Geotechnical Society. Available online: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365946336_PCCH-Arctic_-_Polar_Climate_and_Cultural_Heritage_-_Preservation_and_Restoration_Management_Project_presentation_and_current_results
- Sokolíčková, Z., Meyer, A. and Vlahov, A. 2022. Changing Svalbard: Tracing interrelated socio-economic and environmental change in remote Arctic settlements. *Polar Record*, 58: e23.
- Stammler, F., A. Ivanova and Sidorova, L. 2017. The Ethnography of Memory in East Siberia: Do Life Histories from the Arctic Coast Matter? *Arctic Anthropology* 54(2):1-23.
- Struchkov, A.I. 2005. *Essays on the History of the Bulunskiy Ulus*. Yakutsk: Bichik (in Russian).
- Sutton, M. Q. and Anderson, E. N. 2010. *Introduction to cultural ecology*. Second Edition. Lanham: Alta Mira Press.
- Thornton, T. F. and Manasfi, N. 2010. Adaptation—Genuine and Spurious: Demystifying Adaptation Processes in Relation to Climate Change. *Environment and Society*, 1(1), 132-155.

- Timlin U., J. Ramage, S. Gartler, T. Nordström and Rautio, A. 2022a. Self-rated health, life balance and feeling of empowerment when facing impacts of permafrost thaw – A case study from northern Canada. *Atmosphere*, 13(5), 789.
- Timlin, U., Meyer, A., Nordström, T. and Rautio, A. 2022b. Permafrost thaw challenges and life in Svalbard. *Curr. Opin. Environ Sustain.* 4, 100122.
- Turner, B. L., II, Kasperson, R. E., Matson, P. A., McCarthy, J. J., Corell, R. W., Christensen, L., Eckley, N., Kasperson, J. X., Luers, A., Martello, M. L., Polsky, C., Pulsipher, A. and Schiller, A. 2003. A framework for vulnerability analysis in sustainability science. *PNAS*, 100(14), 8074-8079.
- Vanderlinden, J., Jungsberg, L., Ramage, J., Cordier, M., Wang, S., Doloisio, N., Gartler, S., Meyer, A. and Vullierme, M. 2020. Report on the social representation of permafrost thawing, including economic impact within Arctic communities: a qualitative and quantitative analytical framework. Nunataryuk Deliverable Report 7.4.
- Vogel, B., Yumagulova, L., McBean, G. and Charles Norris, K.A. Indigenous-Led Nature-Based Solutions for the Climate Crisis: Insights from Canada. *Sustainability*, 14, 6725.
- Wannewitz, M. and Garschagen, M. 2023. Collective adaptation to climate change. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 61:101248.
- Wesche, S.D. and Chan, H.M. 2010. Adapting to the Impacts of Climate Change on Food Security among Inuit in the Western Canadian Arctic. *EcoHealth*, 7, 361–373.
- Worden, E., Pearce, T., Gruben, M., Ross, D., Kowana, C. and Loseto, L. 2020. Social-ecological changes and implications for understanding the declining beluga whale (*Delphinapterus leucas*) harvest in Aklavik, Northwest Territories. *Arct. Sci.*, 6, 229–246.

9. Appendix

In the following table we present data on adaptation measures collected in the different study sites.

LONGYEARBYEN, SVALBARD		
Theme and perceived risks	Adaptation measures	Interview quotes
<p>Infrastructure</p> <p>Risks to infrastructure and buildings due to erosion (coastal and hillside) and slides</p> <p>Impacts on housing and other buildings due to structural instabilities, subsidence and settlements</p> <p>Adverse impacts on infrastructure, including roads, the airport strip and the fresh water reserve <i>Isdammen</i>, due to thawing</p>	<p>Fences and nets to prevent mudslides and avalanches</p> <p>Temporal and permanent evacuation of houses in risk zones, relocation of services from risk zones to safe zones</p> <p>Revised areal plan and definition of risk zones</p> <p>Replacing old with new piles (longer piles of steel); establishing ground cooling systems; releveling of existing buildings; insulation of buildings; replacing existing foundations; use of friction piles</p> <p>Import of soil masses from the mainland</p> <p>Erosion prevention in the river <i>Longyarelva</i></p> <p>Measures to prevent coastal erosion at <i>Bykaia</i> and <i>Gamlekaia</i></p> <p>Establishment of monitoring systems</p> <p>Relocation of cabins from the wording shoreline</p>	<p>“And we have to be adaptable, because if we do not adapt it will become a society that cannot make it and will be shut down. We have to be adaptable according to a will to adapt. [How would that transformation look like?] If they would not be willing to invest in this society, by building avalanche security measures, then we would have to shut down big parts here. If they would not have been willing to invest in securing the river [from erosion], then we could not have built any of the buildings there. And then half of the community would have been gone.”</p> <p>“The main problem is in regard to buildings and infrastructure, as the buildings move and destabilize when the permafrost thaws. But we can easily adapt to this - we just have to pile the piles further down, or fundament them on bedrock, this was not done before which is why many buildings struggle today. So adaptation is possible.”</p> <p>“To put buildings on proper foundations is the most important thing we do.”</p> <p>“In Gruvedalen they have important masses from the mainland to build roads and then they have used mainland masses to secure the river from erosion, and then we import masses from the mainland to make the roads.”</p> <p>“Things that were built in the past have to get new foundations, everything</p>

		<p>from pipe routes to houses to street lights.”</p> <p>“From an engineering standpoint, most problems can be solved. [...] So, the infrastructure itself, it will survive. It is manmade, so we can adapt it.”</p> <p>“So there is big movement of the masses here. So it is not about making fundamentals so that things do not move at all, but to make fundamentals that enables everything to move the same.”</p> <p>“And there are examples of people that have had to move their cabins [from the shoreline] twice because the coast starts to erode. They move their cabin and think that “now we move it faaar”, and then after only a short while the erosion has caught up and they have to move it again.”</p>
<p>Health and wellbeing</p> <p>Risk for mental and physical health due to natural hazards</p> <p>Risks related to contamination</p> <p>Risks related to freshwater supply</p>	<p>Physical security measures against natural hazards</p> <p>Monitoring of water quality</p> <p>Examination of possible reserve water sources (for instance a pilot project to develop an osmose system)</p>	<p>“I feel that we have managed to limit it and that people feel safe. [...] Here we have taken it extremely seriously and set the bar high to create safety and we have good solutions for many things. Especially the avalanche warning system is very good. So I experience that people feel safe, but we have discussions where we see that people have reactions to the avalanches, but in general I would say that people feel safe, because they see that the authorities are doing something, that measures are being taken, you see that the town is being moved, that we build avalanche fences and stuff like that. But you have to do something.”</p>
<p>Economy and material wellbeing</p> <p>Increasing costs for protection measures against natural hazards</p>	<p>Planning for change</p> <p>Political prioritization of where to invest and how much</p> <p>Dialogue with central authorities about costs and allocation of funds</p>	<p>“It could become very expensive to live in Longyearbyen. (...) But what is nice here is that we have a political steering of the costs, so that you can define politically how expensive it will be to live here. And I feel that there is good collaboration between the local politicians and the state. They (the state) listen and cooperate.”</p>

<p>Increasing costs for maintenance and repair of buildings and infrastructure</p> <p>Increasing costs related to the construction of new foundations for existing structures</p>	<p>Placing climate change on the public and political agenda to create political awareness in order to finance adaptation measures</p>	<p>“We work to keep the costs down. And with good planning it can work.”</p> <p>“As long as the state wants a Norwegian presence on Svalbard, Longyearbyen will be maintained and invested in.”</p>
<p>Culture and language</p> <p>Loss of and damage to cultural heritage</p>	<p>New foundations for cultural heritage structures; coastal erosion prevention; mapping and monitoring of cultural heritage structures at risk; research on adaptation measures and related values</p>	<p>“It begins with the foundation. To make new foundations (for cultural heritage houses) is a prerequisite for being able to use and live in these houses.”</p>
<p>Water and food security</p> <p>Risks related to freshwater supply: Damage to the damming of the drinking water reserve <i>Isdammen</i> due to permafrost thaw</p>	<p>Monitoring of water quality</p> <p>Monitoring of the dam <i>Isdammen</i> - the freshwater reserve</p> <p>Examination of possibilities to establish a reserve freshwater supply</p>	<p>“So in relation to the permafrost, we are dependent on that the water stays where it should be. We only have one water supply in Longyearbyen. We are starting a pilot project now, to see if we can get an osmose system. [...] But until then we have <i>Isdammen</i>. And we have to protect it well. [...] We depend on that the water does not run out, we don’t have much incoming water in winter. So what we get is in the summer and it is stored in the dam, so if we would have a dam breakage that would be critical.”</p>
<p>Fate control, including planning</p> <p>Uncertainty and unpredictability due to climate change makes planning challenging</p> <p>Risks to the built environment due to natural hazards which impact urban development and planning</p> <p>Risks to the built environment due to a deepening of the active layer and resulting</p>	<p>Use of climate projections and modelling; use of climate change research in planning</p> <p>Revised areal plan and definition of risk zones</p>	<p>“We get new climate scenarios and then it becomes very concrete for us, because then you get new risk zones maps.”</p> <p>“And just in the time that I have been living here we have changed the avalanche risk zones twice. That means that where you could build two years ago is already changed twice.”</p>

infrastructural instabilities and failure		
Recreation and being in nature Risks of natural hazards while being in nature (landslides, mudslides) Loss of hiking trails due to erosion	Avoidance of risky areas; finding new routes and making new paths	“The trail underneath <i>Sarkofagen</i> [a local mountain] has slid out so now it is super steep there and almost impossible to get around that steep section. So now we have to walk down in the moraine or around the back.”
Mobility (travel and transportation) Roads at risk from soil processes, subsidence and erosion Airport runway at risk from subsidence	“Patching” and repair of roads and runway; regulation of how heavy flights can land and how many flight can land in a day Feasibility study for how best to adapt the runway to a changing climate, and potentially move it	“We have weight reductions. So in addition to only six planes a day, we have limitations on how big planes can land here.”
(Energy) Supply No identified risks to energy supply related to permafrost thaw But concerns related to the unsustainability of coal mining and the reliance of the local energy supply on coal	Political decision to close the coal mine and the local coal mining energy plant, to transition towards green energy solutions (the final energy supply has not been defined yet and generators running on diesel will be the interim solution)	
Education and training High turnover of personnel and institutional discontinuity	Establishment of routines and systems to systemize and save knowledge Informal communication between actors (especially with persons with long experience from Svalbard) Courses to address specific challenges, for instance at the University Centre or within institutions	“We have the community plan and that is renewed, so we have tools and the areal plan and the related documents, so that ensures continuity. [...] and then you have to talk to the right people. Kjersti, she has been here very long, she has a lot of history.” “Yeah it is Christiansen and Kjersti who have been initiating the dialogue and they have had good dialogue all along, because Kjersti is responsible for technical infrastructure, and fundamentals and everything that has to do with geotechnics, and she [Christiansen] is doing that stuff down

	Dialogue between the local municipality and the scientific community	there [at the University Centre in Svalbard] and has so much knowledge. So here there has been good dialogue and we will have a new meeting in the autumn.”
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AKLAVIK, NWT, CANADA

Theme and perceived risks	Adaptation measures	Interview quotes
<p>Infrastructure</p> <p>Infrastructure failure, such as houses and cabins that are threatened by erosion</p> <p>Damages to housing and other buildings due to structural instabilities, subsidence and differential settlements</p> <p>Damages to roads, airstrips and industrial infrastructure due to increased thawing</p>	<p>Preventing PFT along river shoreline by modifying vegetation to stabilize ground, f.e. cutting down large trees, putting brush against shore</p> <p>Flood control measures along sea shore</p> <p>Using thermosyphons to cool ground underneath and around structures</p> <p>Snow fencing to prevent snow from accumulating on the road embankment (to prevent permafrost degradation from the road)</p> <p>(Plans for) relocating cabins houses, i.e., from the so-called spit in Tuktoyaktuk to Reindeer Point</p> <p>Moving cabins further away from river or ocean shore</p> <p>Foundation upgrades and using new foundations in construction</p> <p>Devising new ways of building on new permafrost conditions, using new technologies and/or materials</p>	<p>“It's about building in specific places, and then mitigating it as much as possible. So, for here, we're hundreds of years from where the river will get to us, hundreds of years from where the river-. And because we've cut all the trees down, we've extended it, quite a lot. Yeah, I bet you we would double or at least triple the longevity of that bank.”</p> <p>“In preparation for the big flood, that everybody was talking about: So, my camp was closer to the bank last year. I had to cut brush behind my camp, cut lots of brush. And then I had to buy beams to go underneath my house. I had to get chains and come-alongs and straps. And I had to get my house ready and then we hooked it up. And we pulled it back, because the ground was falling (the river shoreline was eroding). My cabin just had enough land beside it for a skiddoo to go by it, that's how close it got. Over the 15 plus years that I was there, I used to have lots more land. So, I moved it about 35 feet back to where it is now, which took eight hours for sure. It was just so tiring work. But that's what we need to do. That's how we're trying to adapt to this land falling all over. I had to cut brush, I had to buy this, buy that – all our time and effort was put into moving my house last year.”</p> <p>“And the thing is when you live out here you live it. Yeah, I've watched the permafrost every day. I dig in it. Yeah, I</p>

	<p>Drawing on Indigenous knowledge and building techniques and technologies, such as covering ice houses with peat</p> <p>Elevated boardwalks instead of sidewalks (f.e. Mayo and Dawson City, Yukon)</p> <p>Shoreline protection against coastal erosion using f.e. structures such as slabs or tyres, or beach nourishment</p> <p>Increasing height of access road to limit flooding impact</p> <p>Elevating e.g. freezers and generators because of increased probability of floods in the camp</p> <p>Improving waste dump, f.e. installing garbage press</p> <p>New road construction methods, f.e. roads made of stone to prevent breaks due to ice freeze/thaw</p> <p>Challenges: Lack of knowledge and knowledge transfer, lack of manpower</p>	<p>pull my food out of it every day. So, I noticed things like, you know what, let's plant some grass here. Yeah, let's just throw 100 bucks worth of grass here. Let's throw some willows in."</p>
<p>Health and wellbeing</p> <p>Concerns for injuries or loss of lives, and additional strains on health caused by changes and the need for adaptation</p> <p>Mental Health concerns caused by the situation itself as well as the</p>	<p>Using communication technology such as cell phone boosters, mobile radios etc. to ensure safety while being on the land</p> <p>Using safety-kits and bringing down search & rescue times</p> <p>Using life-jackets when</p>	<p>"I think it's all about communication, letting people know, you know, somebody that does not have a camp, that lives in town, and then I communicate to them what's happening. "When I went out to my camp, I could see this, I could see that" – and just sitting there talking while we're sewing or whatever. It's communication to let everybody know what's happening around us."</p>

<p>additional efforts needed to adapt</p>	<p>boating, installing bat safety training and local safety ambassadors</p> <p>Testing water quality for heavy metals, mercury etc.</p> <p>Testing for food safety in fish and beluga whales</p> <p>Tracking food and animal migration routes</p> <p>Air quality testing in the summer</p> <p>Monitoring ice safety</p>	
<p>Economy and material wellbeing</p> <p>Costs created by damages to roads, airstrips, cabins, houses etc. put an additional strain on individual and communal financial security</p>	<p>Provision of on the land funding</p> <p>Securing (additional) insurances</p> <p>Availability of compensation payments for lost material/damages to cabins etc.</p> <p>Challenges: Rising costs, living off the land is expensive as it is, lack of manpower</p>	<p>“We got some on the land funding to go, you know, for the fall, which is fine. It was it like \$200 in gas and like \$300 in groceries, which was fine. I mean, I'm very thankful for that. But it's absolutely not enough. It's lots of work to try and adapt. It's lots of work to try and live off the land. The land is expensive. I guess it's money being spent the wrong way. Absolutely. We need manpower, we have to get more help to local cabin owners. It's hard to get help nowadays. I spend so much money on buying supplies for my house. Our wood prices up here, our plywood and all that is outrageous. Because of COVID all the wood prices went up.”</p>
<p>Culture and language</p> <p>Concerns for the loss and/or maintenance of cultural, tangible and intangible heritage</p> <p>And concern for cultural vitality, which is negatively affected because time and resources are taken away by necessary adaptation measures</p>	<p>After experiencing problems with permafrost thaw due to a construction maintenance error, the Aurora Research Institute is monitoring ground temperatures underneath the Igloo Church in Inuvik, a building that is considered part of the local heritage</p> <p>Using traditional knowledge to improve construction practices,</p>	<p>“By having an ice house you're able to open up the lid and the heat escapes. And the cold air sinks and goes in. So, actually having an ice house underneath your building will keep the permafrost much more intact.”</p> <p>“I'm experimenting with traditional Indigenous technologies to see if we can build better and more efficient housing in this environment.”</p>

	<p>such as covering ice houses with peat</p> <p>Terminology workshops and outreach products for translation of scientific terms in to Indigenous languages to educate local population</p>	
<p>Water and food security</p> <p>Subsistence is negatively affected because time and resources are taken away by necessary adaptation measures</p> <p>Water quality may be affected by increased turbidity and contaminants, causing uncertainties</p>	<p>Investment of time: Hunters take more time to find moose who hide better behind higher willows</p> <p>Implementation of fishing and hunting quotas</p> <p>Protecting ice houses by covering them with peat</p> <p>Elevating e.g. freezers and generators because of increased probability of floods in camps</p> <p>Improvement of sewer system</p> <p>Testing water quality (in fish bearing lakes)</p> <p>Testing fish and beluga for contaminants</p> <p>Modification of travel routes: Land users take more time because they need to go around large slumps</p> <p>(Planning for increased) protection of subsistence harvest rights and ecosystem rights, by which are meant animal rights and rights of other than human beings such as mountains, lakes, rivers etc.</p>	<p>“Sometime moose will run into the willows and hunters can’t follow them. You can’t really do anything about it, I just keep looking for another moose.”</p> <p>“The ice house in Tuktoyaktuk is now closed to tourists to prevent any accidents from happening.”</p>

<p>Fate control, including planning</p> <p>Planning needs to be adapted to changing circumstances</p> <p>Risk of unpreparedness to slow and sudden changes</p> <p>Acceleration of change poses a challenge to fate control, people feel that there is no choice but to adapt and that there is nothing they can do about the developments.</p>	<p>In a sense, all adaptation & mitigation measures are a form of fate control and require planning. Some adaptation measures such as planning for flood control based on scientific evaluations of coastal erosion, for example, and planning for moving houses eventually, can take place long before the need actually arises. Local, regional and national entities plan for permafrost thaw induced changes, see for example the NWT Climate Change Strategic Plan, the ISR Climate Change Strategy etc.</p> <p>Challenges: Communities feel that there has been a lot of research but not enough consequent, research-based actions taken, sometimes leading to research-fatigue. At the same time the need for research is acknowledged. Some people express wish for a master plan and it's large-scale execution</p>	<p>"Like it's, everything is changing and you have to learn to adapt to it. We have no choice, right? We got to try and figure out ways of how do we live like this."</p> <p>"We need to try and mitigate this. I don't know how we could do it. But if we get the word out on okay, this plant works, this plant has the strongest and then after that we could figure out okay, how do we distribute it to everybody in the Delta because the old Delta is falling apart care. So, I think research needs to be done on how could we mitigate and help combat owners you know, try and save the land because it just eroding and melting."</p> <p>"We need action! Like we've been researched to death, you know, like, I've been on hunters and trappers board and stuff like that and we'd say okay, Inuvik, the Delta Arctic has been researched to death. Okay, we need some action now. Like we had researchers for years and years nears, come up here. We need action. Yeah. Enough of this research, this has been researched to death. We need help."</p>
<p>Recreation and being in nature</p> <p>Brushes, especially willows grow thicker and higher, making it harder to move across the land</p> <p>The ground and vegetation has become softer making it harder to walk across the tundra for example while berry picking and also causing more of an impact on the ground and</p>	<p>Some hiking trails may not be used temporarily due to closures, entailing a modification of usage of recreational trails and recreation means</p> <p>Being more careful and attentive while travelling across the land</p> <p>Cruise-ship tourists are asked to either stay on the gravel shore or to spread out instead of walking in</p>	<p>"What I noticed over the years as the vegetation is getting softer and people walk on the grassy areas you could see the footprints behind when they're walking in in a single line. So now we tell them to spread out or to stick to the shore."</p>

vegetation when walking across the land.	single lines on Herschel Island/Qikiqtaruk	
<p>Mobility (travel and transportation)</p> <p>Travel routes across the land and waters change due to erosion and slumping, travel becomes more unpredictable and dangerous</p> <p>Road damage can interrupt access to camps and recreational sites</p>	<p>Snow fencing to prevent snow from accumulating on the road embankment (to prevent permafrost degradation from the road)</p> <p>New road construction techniques, such as roads made of stone to prevent breaks due to ice.</p> <p>Being more careful and attentive while traveling across the land and driving on roads</p> <p>Building elevated boardwalks (instead of regular sidewalks)</p> <p>Increasing height of access road to limit flooding impact</p> <p>Repavement of roads</p> <p>Maintenance of subsidence issues on airport</p> <p>Along the Dempster Highway and Inuvik-Tuktoyaktuk Highway communities/municipalities collaborate with scientists, as well as the Indigenous monitoring programs (f.e. ITH Monitors), who are monitoring temperatures and changes along the highways</p>	<p>“You go to some hunting rounds and you notice the slumping of areas where you travel. And then when you go back on the hillside, inside there is the erosion, it is having an effect on the travel. Because now rather than looking out on the land, you got to keep your eyes focused for something that you may fall into. Right? Yeah, I was driving, using a skiddoo one time up there. Driving and looking at the land and: Hm, that looks nice and smooth, I'll try to go across there. So I started going across there and next thing, there was some great slump in the middle of the land.”</p>
<p>(Energy) Supply</p> <p>Damages inflicted by floods, erosion and active layer deepening to energy infrastructure such as electricity poles, generators, etc.</p>	<p>New wind energy, solar, and natural gas projects are being developed in the region. However, there is very little discussion of reducing emissions in private life, for example by not letting cars run outdoors during winter</p>	<p>“We make sure to put our generators far enough from the shore now, to prevent them from falling in to the river.”</p>

	<p>time, because the general understanding is that local residents can do rather very little in their private lives to reduce the global warming</p> <p>Elevating generators to prevent flood damage or moving generators far enough from river or ocean shore to prevent them of getting damaged or lost due to erosion</p>	
<p>Education and training</p> <p>Intergenerational knowledge transfer is threatened by increasingly changing conditions, traditional Indigenous knowledge has become more unreliable because weather and ground (and thus travel) conditions become increasingly unpredictable</p> <p>Knowledge transfer concerning adaptation practices between local organizations and between individuals and families is not always satisfactory</p>	<p>Youth can teach older generations about use of new technology that can help with navigating on the land. In turn, Elders pass on their knowledge about safely being on the land to Youth.</p> <p>Important issues concerning landscape and other ecosystem changes are discussed in local workshops, meetings etc.</p> <p>Individuals try to find innovative solutions for stabilizing the ground, and develop new construction methods, using new technologies and Indigenous knowledge</p>	<p>“You know, we have to do our own research of: “Okay, so there's so much landslides, is there something I could plant around my camp to hold the ground together?” Like something with strong roots, is what I was thinking. So, I put around just plain grass seed, to see. Something that has strong roots that can hold that ground there. Because the ground is falling all over the place. We can't just put thermistors all over the Delta and let it freeze. Because that's not going to work. I mean, we need something that does the job on its own.”</p>
ILULISSAT, DISKO BAY, WEST GREENLAND		
Theme and perceived risks	Adaptation measures	Interview quotes
<p>Infrastructure</p> <p>Higher costs of repair and maintenance due to failure</p> <p>Heavy weight on permafrost damaged</p>	<p>Building permanent roads on bedrock</p> <p>Purchase of material that has proven well on foreign continents</p>	<p>“The roads are very wavy, and it is very expensive to repair, so it becomes a piecemeal repair.”</p> <p>“Only roads can be built on permafrost here.”</p>

<p>infrastructure can cause collapse</p> <p>Damage to housing, including cracks, and doors and windows that cannot close properly</p> <p>Collapsing sewage and water lines, and damage to masts, light poles, and pipes</p> <p>Worsening road conditions, including pot holes and crooked roads</p> <p>Increasingly confined space for infrastructure and residential construction.</p>	<p>Placing more (pipes and wires) above ground, e.g. sewage</p> <p>Using windows with plastic frames to avoid rot</p> <p>Using soil to create an insulating layer to prevent thawing of the frozen ground</p> <p>Using heat sensors to monitor the temperature of the frozen ground</p> <p>Placing cooling system under slumping floor</p>	<p>“They used to remove the permafrost a couple of meters, fill in with gravel, and place ventilation underneath the gravel.”</p> <p>“Access roads can be built on permafrost, and temporary hauling roads. We just level out the temporary roads (access, hauling).”</p> <p>“Some of the roads could be built on permafrost rather than bedrock (as it is) to save money.”</p> <p>“The problem is that the budget for this type of road is just not big enough, and even if they increased the budget ten-fold it would still not be enough, so it is not realistic to think that this will ever happen. But I know that in earlier days they placed isolation under the road and that seems to have had a positive effect, and the road stayed relatively flat.”</p> <p>“Roads are repaired by filling the holes after the snow and ice has melted and the holes appear.”</p> <p>“In Qaanaaq houses have wood foundations, and this makes it easier for us to fix the house. We lift the house; we lay some wood under it. We have done this to five houses in the last 2 years.”</p> <p>“Releveling of houses (it’s a cheap way) and a new method here.”</p> <p>“Yes, plastic windows, we are talking about this now, and the cost. They’re cheap, at an affordable cost, and they are better than most of the tree layered you can get. Because they stay in form. So, they are a favorite product for us - they don't rot.”</p>
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<p>Health and wellbeing</p> <p>Vehicle accidents</p> <p>Health risks related to water quality</p>	<p>Keeping a safety officer on staff</p> <p>Use of sea ice instead of tap water</p> <p>Training of drivers for special conditions</p>	<p>“We always keep safety in mind with respect to big holes and steep slopes in construction areas.”</p> <p>“My parents have found their own ways of dealing with problems such as lack of good water quality; we sail out and collect large pieces of ice that we bring back to town, to our home, and we use it instead of the tap water – to avoid possible pollution and chemical stuff.”</p>
<p>Economy and material wellbeing</p> <p>Higher costs due to permafrost thaw related impacts</p> <p>Difficulties meeting financial requirements for public and private sectors</p>	<p>Careful prioritization, and taking care to limit the negative trade-offs</p> <p>Public/private partnerships to share risks</p> <p>Introduction of innovative risk and business models</p>	<p>“To deal with financial risks, one could look at different risk models, e.g. models of shared financial risk between client and contractor; could be part of the competition for a contract bid.”</p> <p>“If you are going to dig deeper, take a look at the machinery and don't choose the cheap solution.”</p> <p>“Our limit is the money. The building has to be cheap. We address it when we find problems and solve it with the means we have, the money and the tools.”</p> <p>“It often ends in small fixes because of lack of financial resources, especially after the municipality amalgamations, and Ilulissat now belonging to a larger municipality.”</p> <p>“Our municipality gets a small bag of money, one at a time, not at all enough</p>

		to do anything but small fixes, not enough to build a sustainable infrastructure.”
Culture and recreation Less dog sledding and snowmobiling	Making changes to travel routes to hunting and fishing ground	“It takes us longer to get to our fishing ground because we now must take a different route with the dogsled and our snowmobile (less snow).”
Water and food security Key risks perceived Unsafe water	Monitoring of water quality Boiling water for home use Moving the water reservoir to a safe location Moving the water pipes (vandedninger), and building new water purifying system (vand renseanlæg)	“They would like to move the water lake (vandsøen) to another location, because underneath the permafrost there is salt water, and we cannot risk having that mix with the town's drinking water”. “Laboratories are being moved to Nuuk for conducting various tests, e.g. water quality. (not useful for local adaptation).”
Fate control, including planning Challenges in budgeting and decision making, and related critical trade-offs Insufficient financial resources to meet demands for maintenance and repair of municipality structures	More time spent planning Keeping more in stock, or look at older and better models/engines Putting pressure on the government to take action Using specially built vehicles	“Delivery time of spare parts is our main concern.” “To try to address the situation of the road conditions we put pressure on the municipality to get them to dig down deeper rather than simply add more asphalt on top which does not solve the situation.” “We need the types of vehicles that are strongly built but not necessarily built for long-distance driving.” “We spend more time planning.”
Education and training Lack of specialists to meet need Risks related to recruitment and retention, and loss of critical knowledge and technical experience Risks from gaps in education and knowledge to meet growing challenge	More training to meet new demands. Information campaigns Better access to information Training and education of the drivers for the special road conditions, so they adapt to the special conditions	“We are in need of more information. We need an information campaign.” “Some representatives have visited other Nordic regions and Canada to learn how others adapt to permafrost thaw.” “We train our own mechanics so that we don't have to send equipment out for repair – which takes time.”

	<p>Learning from other permafrost regions in the Arctic; sharing knowledge and workable solutions</p>	<p>“We up qualify our own mechanics so they can do the repairs needed due to permafrost related damage.”</p> <p>“The most common method is training and education of our drivers and the purchase of the right equipment, e.g. a type of vehicles used abroad that are easier to maintain and that have elaborate suspension systems including powerful springs and shock absorbers that are better suited for our use.”</p> <p>“It is important that our drivers adapt to the special conditions; it is not about getting to your destination 10 km faster per hour; that would only increase the vehicle damage and wear and tear here. So, it’s about training and educating our drivers to take special care and drive carefully according to the conditions and avoid the bumps.”</p> <p>“There are places in town where you need to be patient and wait for oncoming traffic to pass to avoid a bump. So, to exercise patience is also a part of the training.”</p> <p>“To some extent the most cost-effective measure you can take is to train your drivers to minimize contact with the affected roads (areas).”</p> <p>“My goal is to pass on knowledge to the young generation, and students, to make sure they are engaged and well-informed about climate change and its impacts. When the adults don't listen we need to reach the young generation. Social media and short films have been effective ways to engage the youth here.”</p> <p>“Educating experts, engineers, and collaboration with the Engineering programme in Sisimiut, could be a solution.”</p>
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<p>Mobility (Travel and Transportation)</p> <p>Frequent damage complicates flow and stability of travel and transport</p> <p>Challenges to getting timely resupply</p> <p>Added stress of increased number of cars on permafrost affected ground.</p>		<p>“It is important that our drivers adapt to the special conditions; it is not about getting to your destination 10 km faster per hour; that would only increase the vehicle damage and wear and tear here. So, it’s about training and educating our drivers to take special care and drive carefully according to the conditions and avoid the bumps.”</p> <p>“There are places in town where you need to be patient and wait for oncoming traffic to pass to avoid a bump. So, to exercise patience is also a part of the training.”</p> <p>“To some extent the most cost-effective measure you can take is to train your drivers to minimize contact with the affected roads (areas).”</p>

REPUBLIC OF SAKHA (YAKUTIYA), NORTH-EAST SIBERIA, RUSSIA

Theme and perceived risks	Adaptation measures	Interview quotes
<p>Infrastructure</p> <p>Destruction of buildings and sacred sites (e.g., due to coastal erosion in Bykovskiy)</p> <p>Malfunctioning of ice roads</p> <p>Decreased reliability and melting of ice cellars</p> <p>Destabilization of individual houses</p> <p>Destabilization and disruption of transport infrastructure</p>	<p>Stopped construction of new buildings and relocation of old one from the areas affected by pft and coastal erosion</p> <p>Delegation of responsibility to authorities</p> <p>Shortening the season of delivery of goods and foods to communities</p> <p>Shortened period of storage of fish and immediate supply of fish to consumers in /by the beginning of summer</p>	<p>“And now we just do not build anything in this direction of the village any more. We do not put up houses there. And we demolish and move all the older buildings standing there to this part of the village. This is the only way ...” (Official, local administration, Bykovskiy)</p> <p>“There is no one else, but authorities who should take care of it...We don’t have such capacity” (Indigenous family, Bykovskiy)</p> <p>“Earlier when we had real cold, we open them [ice roads] in December and now only in January. We need to hurry up to deliver coal, fuels and lubricants.</p>

	<p>Short-term planning and repairs</p> <p>Expert monitoring and assessment</p>	<p>This is problem, especially for the north-eastern part [of Sakha (Yakutiya)]” (Official, Yakutsk)</p> <p>“Ice cellars are melting. Last year, one cellar was flooded. There was rain and lots of precipitation...Ice cellars themselves keep the temperature below zero sufficient for storage only till mid-summer. Later, with -3 or -5, the fish can no longer be preserved” (Official, Bykovskiy)</p> <p>“It [the house] might stand here for another couple of hundreds years...This is long enough for us” (Indigenous family, Bykovskiy)</p> <p>“Of course, the [Permafrost] Institute does its work and looks at how the city, towns, pipelines, railroads and ordinary automobile roads behave” (Expert, Yakutsk)</p>
<p>Health and wellbeing</p> <p>Concern about pollution of water and marine resources due to technological hazards, e.g., industrial pollution, chemical and oil spills (arguable connected to pft)</p> <p>Concern about soil contamination due to outbreak of (dormant) viral diseases (e.g., anthrax) because of the destruction of the cemetery</p> <p>Malfunctioning ice roads</p>	<p>Observing, abstaining from consumption of suspiciously looking water and fish</p> <p>Calling attention of authorities, experts and journalists to the problem of the coastal erosion and its potential threats to health</p> <p>Higher dependence on low quality foods supplied to local stores leading to health problems</p>	<p>“During tides, dirty water comes from upstream, from those dams...Of course, the water looks awful and one can catch yellow fish there” (Indigenous resident, Bykovskiy)</p>
<p>Economy and material wellbeing</p> <p>Economic challenges and financial loss, e.g. due disruptions and higher costs of supply of foods and fuels</p>	<p>Shortening the season of delivery of goods and foods to communities</p> <p>Outmigration: moving out of young people from communities</p>	<p>“Earlier when we had real cold, we open them [ice roads] in December and now only in January. We need to hurry up to deliver coal, fuels and lubricants. This is problem, especially for the north-eastern part [of Sakha (Yakutiya)]” (Official, Yakutsk)</p>

<p>because of malfunctioning ice roads (high snow and shortening period of use)</p> <p>Losses to subsistence economy due to shrinking fishing stocks and loss of pastures because of landscape transformations (swamps, shrubification)</p>		<p>“The generation gap [in agriculture] remains because young people are rarely attracted by such hard work and extreme living conditions. In the Republic [of Sakha (Yakutiya)], we are starting working on raising the standards of life in communities...” (Official, Yakutsk)</p>
<p>Culture and recreation</p> <p>Concern about the loss of the original natural and cultural environment</p> <p>Destruction of the grave yard and infrastructure because of costal erosion</p> <p>Destruction of archeological sites by unregulated extraction and collection of mammoth tusk (appearing because of permafrost thaw)</p>	<p>Reliance on traditional knowledge and practices of adaptation to the changing environment</p> <p>Attempts to fortify the coast at local level</p> <p>Proposed stricter regulations and control</p>	<p>“We have been always living on this [eroding] cape” (Indigenous resident, Bykovskiy)</p> <p>“We tried to undertake the measures for fortification of coasts...but even the republic cannot allocate us so much...It should be some kind of federal [money]”</p>
<p>Water and food security</p> <p>Concern about food security (e.g. fish) stored in ice cellars</p> <p>Concern about shrinking fish stocks because of changing salinity of water due to climate change and pf thaw</p>	<p>Shorter period of storage of fish in ice cellars</p> <p>Fishing in deeper waters farther away from the coast</p>	<p>See above</p> <p>“Because of water desalination near the coast, fish has no food and doesn’t come close, but goes away into the deep sea» (resident, Bykovskiy)”</p>
<p>Fate control, including planning</p> <p>Planning of new infrastructures and resource development on territories with continuous permafrost need to take into consideration expert recommendations</p>	<p>Monitoring condition of roads by construction organizations</p> <p>Expert assessments and recommendations on the use of land and development plans</p> <p>Adoption of the law on protection of permafrost</p>	<p>“Road construction organizations do not want to take mitigation measures that we recommend – they just monitor ...”</p> <p>“There is a center for strategic planning. They call us and ask where and what can be developed. And we write them detailed recommendations about each region and location: e.g., here one cannot develop land because of the ice</p>

<p>Local communities are challenged with the lack of financial resources and decision-making power to mitigate impacts of permafrost thaw</p> <p>Destruction of fragile permafrost-rich lands due to industrial development and overexploitation</p> <p>Controversial and scary information about permafrost and climate change in mass media</p>	<p>and mapping of protected areas/areas with restricted land use</p> <p>Denial or ignorance of permafrost thaw</p> <p>Climate optimism, disregard of coastal erosion</p>	<p>... But they never inform us about their plans.” (expert, Melnikov Institute of Permafrost, RAS, Yakutsk)</p> <p>“Unstable plots of land [with degrading permafrost] should not be developed at all” (expert, Yakutsk)</p> <p>“It seems to me that the permafrost will still remain here...The hotter the weather here, the better it is preserved” (resident, Bykovskiy)</p> <p>“The [Bykov] cape will always stand even if the sea rises...That island may disappear but not the cape...” (resident, Bykovskiy)</p>
<p>Mobility (travel and transportation)</p> <p>Access to fisheries is more complicated because of fish migrations caused by changing quality of water (desalination along the coast)</p> <p>Traveling on the tundra has become dangerous because of the transformation of landscapes (more swamps)</p> <p>Loss of connectivity between and within settlements and camps, e.g., roads may get closed, rivers become unnavigable due to the effects of permafrost thaw</p>	<p>Avoid going fishing out into the sea in bad weather</p> <p>Avoid traveling out in the tundra with snowmobiles in freezing (autumn) and melting (spring) season</p> <p>Finding alternative routes and tightening the time slots of community supply</p>	<p>“There are strong winds and big waves. When the winds are that strong, they don’t go fishing” (Indigenous fishermen, Bykovskiy)</p> <p>“When you travel to your fishing spot with your “Buran”[snow mobile] on the tundra, you may notice that a river bank you drove along last year, doesn’t exist anymore – either it melted or was washed away. Once a man with a snow mobile disappeared this way” (Indigenous resident, Tiksi)</p>
<p>Education and training</p> <p>Low public and political awareness about consequences of permafrost thaw</p>	<p>Sharing expert knowledge about permafrost, educating public and politicians</p>	<p>“Only scientists have understood [the consequences of permafrost degradation], but politicians are still getting there“ (expert, Melnikov Permafrost Institute, Yakutsk)</p>